

Proceedings

**STATE OF THE ECOLOGICAL RESEARCH
ON SOIL SCIENCE AND LAND USE
IN SLOVAK REPUBLIC AND IN AUSTRIA**

April 6 - 8, 1994

Soil Fertility Research Institute, Bratislava,
Societas Pedologica, Slovak Republic
Österreichische Bodenkundliche Gesellschaft

together

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*Ass. -Prof.Dipl.-Ing.Dr.
Eduard Klaghofer
President of the Austrian
Soil Science Society*

Dear Colleges,

it is a great pleasure for me to be here in Bratislava at the Soil Fertility Research Institute and I bring the best greetings from the Austrian Soil Science Society.

It is the first time, that the Austrian Soil Science Society has arranged a common scientific conference with the Societas Pedologica. This meeting gives us the opportunity to discuss soil related problems in the broad sense of soil ecology. Therefore I hope this symposium will be the beginning of a fruitful exchange of ideas and scientific experiences between our societies.

At least let me give my thanks to the Soil Fertility Research Institute for hosting this conference and all for coming.

HEAVY METALS IN SOIL - AN ASPECT OF THE UPPER AUSTRIAN SOIL MONITORING PROGRAM

K.AICHBERGER, G.HOFER and U.GRUBER

SUMMARY

Due to the law for soil conservation a soil monitoring program was performed in Upper Austria. There were selected systematically 880 control sites from the agricultural area of Upper Austria and all sites and soil profiles were described and about 2000 samples were taken from surface and deeper soil layers. The program of analysis covered soil physical, chemical and microbiological parameters. Following heavy metals were analysed where at the median concentrations in ppm/d.m. were: Mn 740, Cu 18, Zn 76, Co 10, Cr 34, Ni 21, Pb 23, Cd 0.26, Hg 0.10, As 8.2, Tl 0.3, Se 0.24, Mo 0.4 and V 42. The range of data was high but the limit values according to the Upper Austrian law for soil conservation and ÖNORM L1075 were only exceeded on less than 1 to 2 % of all sites. Normally the heavy metal contents of soils depends on parent material even though accumulations of lead, cadmium and mercury could be established on 60 - 80 % of all sites.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Aufgrund des Bodenschutzgesetzes 1991 wurde in den vergangenen drei Jahren in Oberösterreich ein umfangreiches Bodenuntersuchungsprogramm durchgeführt. Nach einem systematischen Raster wurden 880 Meßstellen auf landwirtschaftlich genutzten Böden ausgewählt, standörtlich und bodenkundlich beschrieben und an die 2000 Bodenproben aus mehreren

Tiefenstufen entnommen. Das Analysenprogramm erstreckte sich auf bodenphysikalische, -chemische und -mikrobiologische Parameter. Folgende umweltrelevanten Schwermetalle wurden untersucht, wobei die mittleren Konzentrationen in mg pro kg Trockensubstanz wie folgt betragen: Mn 740, Cu 18, Zn 76, Co 10, Cr 34, Ni 21, Pb 23, Cd 0.26, Hg 0.10, As 8.2, Tl 0.3, Se 0.24, Mo 0.4 und V 42. Der Streubereich der Daten war hoch, aber die Schwermetallgrenz- oder Richtwerte nach dem ÖÖ Bodenschutzgesetz respektive der ÖNORM L 1075 wurden auf weniger als 1-2 % aller Meßstellen überschritten. Üblicherweise hängen die Schwermetallgehalte der Böden in erster Linie von der Zusammensetzung des Ausgangsmaterials ab, wenngleich für Blei, Cadmium und Quecksilber anthropogene Anreicherungen auf 60-80 % aller Standorte festgestellt werden konnten.

SÚHRN

Na základe zákona o ochrane pôdy z roku 1991 sa na území Horného Rakúska v posledných troch rokoch vykonáva rozsiahly program výskumu pôdy. Podľa systematického rastu bolo zvolených 880 pozorovacích miest na poľnohospodárskej pôde, bol vykonaný stanovištný a pôdoznalecký popis a bolo odobraných 2000 vzoriek z viacerých hĺbok pôdneho profilu. Program analýz sa zameriaval na pôdnofyzikálne, chemické a mikrobiologické parametre. Pozorovaniam boli potrebné nasledujúce ťažké kovy, relevantné v životnom prostredí, pričom sa zistili stredné koncentrácie v mg na kg sušiny: Mn 740, Cu 18, Zn 76, Co 10, Cr 34, Ni 21, Pb 23, Cd 0.26, Hg 0.10, As 8.2, Tl 0.3, Se 0.24, Mo 0.4 a V 42. Rozsah údajov bol vysoký, ale hranica obsahu ťažkých kovov, či smerná hodnota podľa rakúskeho zákona na ochranu pôdy, alebo normy ÖNORM L 1075 boli menej ako 1-2 % prekročené. Obvykle závisia obsahy ťažkých kovov v pôde v prvom rade na zložení východzieho materiálu, hoci pri olove, kadmiu a ortuti sa na 60-80 % všetkých stanovišť jedná o antropogénne obohatenie.

1. MONITORING PROGRAM

Since January 1992 a law for the conservation of soil exists in the federal country of Upper Austria (OÖ. Bodenschutzgesetz, 1991). This law was established to preserve soils in general to protect them against harmful substances and to improve soil quality and fertility. In article 22 there are required especial investigations on soil nutrient supply, contamination of soils by toxic substances and on the effect of soil erosions. Due to this investigations a report on state of soils had to be prepared by the local government in 3 year -intervals.

So in the last 3 years a comprehensive soil monitoring program according to the proposal of Blum et al. (1989) was carried out in Upper Austria for the first time. Investigations were extended on soil physical, chemical and microbiological parameters. The program of work to was:

- selection of control sites
- description of sites and soil profiles
- soil sampling
- soil analyses
- report on data

The selection of control sites followed a systematic screen where at the distance from site to site was about 4 km in square. Additional sites were established at the cross of diagonals of the square so that the actual distance between the control areas was 2,75 km. Altogether over the whole country 880 sites were established - 441 on grassland and 439 on arable land. Forest areas, non cultivated land or over built areas were not included in the investigation program. The form of a control site is a circle area of 314 m² with the diameter of 20 meters. The centre of the circle was measured exactly from at least to fixed - points outside of the area and fit out with a metal marking. Every site was located exactly in a map. In the northern part of all sites a soil profile was opened and site and profile were described

according to the Austrian guideline for soil cartography. The model of a site is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Model of a control site (\varnothing 20 m, 314m²)

From the 314 m² area soil samples were taken randomly by an auger or from the profile walls from surface layer and 2-3 further soil layers. There were sampled the layers 0-5, 5-10, 10-20 and 20-40 cm on grassland, respectively 0-20, 20-40 and 40-60 cm on arable land. Altogether from 880 sites about 2000 samples were taken prepared for chemical analysis. The program of analysis covered the determination of pH-value, soil texture, organic matter, total nitrogen, available nutrients, cation-exchange-capacity, heavy metals (total and available amounts), organic compounds like PCBs, PAH, or organochloric pesticides and some physical and microbiological parameters.

2. HEAVY METALS

From about 60 heavy metals occurring in nature especially elements with toxic relevance and importance for the environment were investigated. So all soil samples were analysed for manganese, copper, zinc, cobalt, nickel, chromium, lead and cadmium. Selected sites (n=236) were analysed additionally for mercury, arsenic, selenium, molybdenum, thallium and vanadium. Soil samples were digested in reversed aqua regia or in perchloric acid and the determination of heavy metals was done by ICP, AAS, graphite furnace or hydride - and cold vapour technic. The reason for the investigation was:

- to get a view about the heavy metal contents of soils in general
- to estimate the influence of the geological material and
- to find out possible contaminations of local sites or areas in Upper Austria

Due to the investigations of Aichberger et al. (1982) the occurrence of heavy metals in soils depends mainly on the parent material if there are no other pollutions. There are low concentrations in granite and gneiss, medium values in sedimentary rocks and high contents in basalt and basic magmatic rocks. During the weathering heavy metals are soluted, distributed, leached or accumulated in soil horizons. Beside this natural sources heavy metals reach soils also from atmospheric deposition, from mineral and organic fertilizers, waste products and pesticides. The input of heavy metals via atmosphere (originate from traffic, industries, burning processes) varies from less than 1 g up to more than 1000 g per hectare and year depending on element and situation. Still higher loadings can be applied to soils by the use of special fertilizers, sewage sludge and waste compost (Aichberger, 1989).

3. RESULTS OF INVESTIGATION

In table 1 the heavy metal levels of Upper Austrian soils (surface layer) are compiled. There are listed minimum and maximum values, median and 10 -

and 90 percentile values to see the range of data and to estimate the most frequent concentrations. Additionally there are listed tolerable (limit) values according to the law for soil conservation and Ö-Norm L 1075 - guideline (1993). The range of data is wide, sometimes more than a factor of one hundred. Between 10 and 90 percentile data range is reduced significantly to the factor of 2-3. Comparing the results of maximum values and tolerable contents it is to establish that almost all heavy metals exceed the limit values. But the actual number of control sites where tolerable contents are reached or exceeded is low. In 1 % of all cases copper, zinc and mercury, in 1 % chromium, nickel and in 2 % cadmium exceeds the limit values. Cobalt, selenium, arsenic, molybdenum and thallium do not exceed, or only for some exceptions.

Table 1: Heavy metal contents of soils in Upper Austria (mg/kg).

Element	Min	10-Perz	Med	90-Perz	Max	Limit-values
manganese	200	400	740	1350	5600	—
copper	3	11	18	28	144	100
zinc	30	57	76	116	330	300
cobalt	1	6	10	14	26	50
chromium	6	19	34	52	420	100
nickel	1	7	21	33	260	60
lead	8	15	23	42	150	100
cadmium	0,07	0,17	0,26	0,56	6,9	1,0
mercury	0,04	0,06	0,10	0,24	2,7	1,0
arsenic	1	3,0	8,2	15	53	20
thallium	0,1	0,19	0,29	0,68	1,7	1,0
selenium	0,01	0,15	0,24	0,46	1,1	(5,0)
molybdenum	0,03	0,20	0,40	0,70	13	(5,0)
vanadium	14	28	42	72	120	(50)

If the results of investigations are considered with respect to the location of sites in many cases good relations between the parent material of soil development and heavy metal contents could be observed. Especially the con-

tents of chromium, nickel, arsenic and thallium are very different in different regions of Upper Austria and the values correspond closely with geological material. Normally soils in the Bohemian Massif (granite, gneiss) have really low heavy metals levels (except of Zn and Tl), soils in the Molasse area (marine sediments, sandstone, marl, loess, loam etc.) show medium values and the highest concentrations we can find Flysch and Limestone alps. So the heavy metal contents of soils in different regions can be demonstrated very well by map-graphs. For example in the Bohemian Massif the Ni-values are mostly below 15 ppm, while soils in the Molasse vary between 15 and 30 ppm and in the Limestone alps the Ni-contents are frequently higher than 50 ppm (Hofer und Aichberger, 1993).

The levels of selenium and molybdenum are rather low in Upper Austrian soils and in many cases deficiencies for these elements have to be assumed. One question of the investigation was if the heavy metal contents of soils are more influenced by natural geological sources or by contaminations from outside. Because heavy metals in soils are translocated hardly we tried to evaluate the values of the surface layer by investigating soil layers below. The results are quite different and depending on type of element. For example cobalt, nickel and chromium are distributed very evenly in the soil horizons or sometimes the values in deeper layers even higher than in surface layer. This means that these heavy metals originate exclusively from parent material. Copper and zinc contents are increasing slightly from bottom to the surface layer so that for some sites depositions had to be assumed. Problems exist for lead, cadmium and mercury. For these metals concentrations in surface layers are significant higher than in the layers below so that an influence by anthropogene immissions (from traffic, industry, fertilization, pesticides etc.) is evident.

By the reason of the heavy metal concentrations in a depth of 40-60 cm the natural geological "background level" of lead, cadmium and mercury was calculated and this values were related to the observed contents in surface layer. The results of this calculation are interesting and surprising. On 60-80 % of all sites accumulations of lead, cadmium and mercury could be

established where at the ÖNORM-guideline for soil contamination is sometimes exceeded too (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Accumulation of cadmium in Upper Austrian soils (surface layer)

Summarizing the results it is to establish that the contents of nickel, chromium, cobalt, arsenic and thallium in soils mostly depend on parent material and there are no man made accumulations. For copper, zink and manganese there can be found some accumulations as well as deficiencies on some sites in Upper Austria. The concentrations of selenium and molybdenum are rather low in general but accumulations of lead, cadmium and mercury in surface soils were found at many sites.

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Name und Anschrift der Verfasser:

Karl AICHBERGER, Gerhard HOFER und Ulrike GRUBER
Bundesanstalt f. Agrarbiologie
Wieningerstr. 8
A-4020 Linz
Austria

SOIL SCIENCE IN SLOVAK REPUBLIC, PRESENT STATE AND PERSPECTIVES

P. BIELEK

SUMMARY

During the history of Slovakian pedology, the most important period was started after second world war. In 1960 the Soil Fertility Research Institute in Bratislava was established. The General Soil Survey of agricultural soils was performed from 1960 to 1970 with density 1 profile per 14 ha of soils. The first Soil Map of Slovak Republic (1:500 000) was published in 1973. In the seventies the theoretical principles of soil production potential were developed and explained on the maps (1:5000). Simultaneously the soil pollution survey was started. From the 1955 (up to now) the agrochemical testing of agricultural soils has permanently performed in 5-years (3-years respectively) cycles. The Geographical Information System about soil properties was created concerning the huge data base and graphical pictures (maps). The monitoring of soil properties was started in the beginning of nineties. In the field of pedology relatively good level of development was achieved in Slovak Republic until now. The following activities are important in improvement of theory and in result interpretation practices. Close personal and institutional contacts are need for our more intensive acceptance within the international research projects. The compatible position with western European countries we have to achieve on the field of methodology, limits, standards, and data processing, as well.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Die für die slowakische Bodenkunde wichtigste Periode begann nach dem Zweiten Weltkrieg. Im Jahre 1960 wurde das jetzige Forschungsinstitut für Bodenfruchtbarkeit in Bratislava gegründet. Eine umfassende pedologische Forschung erfolgte in den Jahren 1960 bis 1970 und zwar durch eine Bodenaufnahme mit einer Stichdichte von einem Einschlag pro 14 ha als Grundlage der ersten Bodenkarte der Slowakei (Maßstab 1:500 000), die im Jahre 1973 herausgegeben wurde. In den 70er Jahren wurden die theoretischen Unterlagen für die Bewertung des Produktionspotentials der Böden der Slowakei und dessen kartenmäßige Präsentation (Maßstab 1:5000) erarbeitet. Gleichzeitig begann das Forschungsprogramm über die Bodenverunreinigung. Ab 1955 wird eine permanente agrochemische Bodenkontrolle in einem 5jährigen (teils 3jährigen) Zyklus vorgenommen. Ein geographisches Informationssystem über die Bodeneigenschaften mit einer umfangreichen Datenbasis, geeignet für die Herstellung von Karten, wurde aufgebaut. Mit den 90er Jahren begann der Aufbau eines Monitoringsystems über die Bodeneigenschaften, dank dessen nun ein guter Kenntnisstand der Böden der Slowakei erreicht wurde. In Zukunft wird es notwendig sein, die theoretischen Kenntnisse zu vertiefen und die Interpretationen der Forschungsergebnisse zu vervollkommen. Engere persönliche und institutionelle Kontakte sind im Interesse der slowakischen bodenkundlichen Forschung bei der Lösung der internationalen Forschungsaufgaben erforderlich. So soll eine Kompatibilität der Methoden, der Limits, der Normen und der Datenbasisoutputs mit den übrigen Ländern Europas erreicht werden.

SÚHRN

Najväčší rozvoj slovenskej pedológie bol zaznamenaný po II. svetovej vojne. V roku 1960 bol založený dnešný Výskumný ústav pôdnej úrodnosti, Bratislava. Komplexný pôdoznalecký prieskum bol vykonávaný v rokoch 1960-1970 s hustotou pozorovania 1 sonda na 14 ha pôdy. Prvá Pôdna mapa Slovenska

(1:500 000) bola vydaná v roku 1973. V sedemdesiatych rokoch boli vypracované teoretické princípy hodnotenia produkčného potenciálu pôd Slovenska, vrátane vyjadrenia na mapách (1:5000). Súčasne sa začalo s prieskumom znečistenia pôd. Od roku 1955 sa permanentne vykonáva agrochemické skúšanie pôd v 5 ročných (resp. 3 ročných) cykloch. Vytvorený je geografický informačný systém o vlastnostiach pôd s obrovskou bázou údajov a grafickým vyjadrením (na mapách). Monitoring vlastností pôd sa začal vykonávať od začiatku deväťdesiatych rokov. Slovenské pôdoznanectvo dosiahlo relatívne dobrú úroveň poznania. Do budúcnosti treba prehĺbiť teoretické poznatky a zdokonaľiť interpretácie výsledkov výskumu. Tesnejšie osobné a inštitucionálne kontakty sú potrebné v záujme výraznejšej účasti slovenského pôdoznanectva na riešení medzinárodných výskumných projektov. Dosiahnuť treba kompatibilitu metód výskumu, limitov, noriem a výstupov z databáz s krajinami Západnej Európy.

Is difficult to speak about history, present state and about future, as well within the brief space of proceeding contribution. Everybody of interested could put emphasis another information, his/her own personal point of view. Therefore it is not my privilege to write about so important and simultaneously complicated questions, too.

Within the Slovakian soil science history the most important time of development was started after second world war. It was time when really scientific fundament of soil science were established and finally first really scientific monographs about Slovakian soils were published (Hroššo, F: Soil Science, 1958; Soil Fertility and its improvement, 1961).

During period after second world war history the changes in policy and economy of Slovak Republic were started as a results of Soviet Union political influences in the territory of former Czechoslovakia. New principles and topics of political development in Slovak Republic favorized the new types of agriculture and evoked the fundamental changes in political and public relations to

soil. Under influence of new political situation the agriculture in Slovak Republic was collectivized and cooperative and state farms were established. Large scale forms were more and more frequent in agriculture of Slovak Republic. High agriculture production and sufficient nourishment of inhabitants were the main political aims of this period. Self-sufficiency in food production was declared as a one of main important topics of our way to socialist type of state regime. From the highest political levels were preferred ideas about the necessities to protect the resources of soil and to use the soil with the biggest effects in processes of plant production. Inside of mentioned favourable political climate in relations to the soil were created good conditions for supported thinking about the importance of soil in the social and economy aspects of country development and about the soil effects in the living standard of our inhabitants.

Successively were matured situations to establish a official scientific institution on the field of soil science in Slovak Republic. In summer time of 1960 Soil Science Institute was founded in Bratislava with following perspectives with human, financial and technical background development for research and advisory activities which were focused on rational soil use and protection of soil cover resources. Simultaneously in Agriculture University at Nitra and another research institutions the pedology was supported and apparently developed concerning all aspects of soil science in agriculture and environment protection. Now, Slovakian soil science is well known not only inside of country, but in abroad, as well.

From the science point of view, after world war the pedology was developed under Soviet Union influences in the theory and practical interpretations, too. Moreover, all theoretical and practical aspects of our pedology had to respect large scale type of farming in Slovak Republic. These influences were main reasons of no compatible research activities, norms, standards, classifications, definitions and practical recommendations in comparison with another (mainly western) countries in Europe.

What about concrete results of Slovakian soil science? General soil survey of Slovakian agricultural soil was so far most important activity which was performed by Soil Fertility Research Institute at Bratislava during the years from 1960 to 1970. During the relatively long time of survey and with the help of serious financial budget were obtained relatively detailed information about the agricultural soil properties in Slovak Republic with the density of observation 1 soil profile per 14 ha of agricultural land. More than 10 000 soil maps (1:5000) and several millions data resulted like map and data base about Slovakian agricultural soils. Archive of soil samples is following important heritage of soil survey. By the way, at the beginning of seventies Slovak Republic have belonged to the countries with the most precise information about soil cover of territory and thanks to next survey activities it is the truth up to now. Soil maps and general interpretations for improve of soil use and farming systems were immediately offered to individual cooperative and state farms such as implementation of actual informations into the Slovakian agriculture. The soil survey results were important and helpful factors on the way to improve the decision making activities in agriculture and to achieve the higher standards and results in agriculture practice. From scientific point of view the soil survey was a decisive step on the way to the high level of knowledge and with respect to general development of soil science in Slovak Republic. During the soil survey activities many new pedologists have been educated and those which were skilled in theory, they obtained new practical experiences. Results of the soil survey were helpful to higher level of traditional branches of pedology and moreover the backgrounds for new research activities were created.

Later on, both agricultural and forest soil surveys information were commonly evaluated and finally interpreted to the Soil Map of Slovak Republic on the scale 1:500 000 (1973). Several following regional soil maps were published in Slovak Republic as well. The latest approximation of Soil Map of Slovak Republic was published in the scale 1:400 000 in 1993.

Based on soil survey data collection many other new important interpretations were created, published and implemented to the practice, too. At the first place the theoretical principles for evaluation of Slovakian soil production potential were decided and explained on the maps (scale 1:5000). On the territory of Slovak Republic were determined more than 7000 types of pedo-ecological units which are defined as a function of soil and ecological properties and characterized by seven number codes. On the base of pedo-ecological units the principles of subsidiary and taxes in our agriculture were deduced and the price of soil is determined, as well. Pedo-ecological units are used like fundamental principles in optimization of many aspect of farming systems. With the help of the units, the projects of land use are planned, the crop rotations are recommended, the rates of fertilizers are advised for concrete soil blocks and cultivated plants. The principles of state policy in agriculture are determined with the help of pedo-ecological units, too. On the base of pedo-ecological units the territory of Slovak Republic was divided among 12 regions with respect to previous conditions for following development of agriculture and another related human activities, as well.

The soil survey results were systematically complemented by any other following information about Slovak soil properties. One of the most important the data base about soil pollution was created. The survey of soil pollution in Slovak Republic has shown concrete "hot spots" regions of contamination. Only 30-40 thousand ha of agricultural land are over limit contaminated (1, 2 - 1,6 % of total agricultural soils). Polluted soils are permanently observed and investigated with the aim to solve the problems.

With the very fruitful impacts was/is active the Agrochemical Soil Testing. It started in 1955 and it is performed until now. Up to 1981 was performed in 5-year cycles, between 1981-1989 in 3-year cycles and at this time the 11th 5 year cycle is being finished. Available forms of phosphorus, potassium and magnesium, pH and need for liming are determined in the top layer of each block of agricultural soils. The results are evaluated in 5-year (3-year respectively) cycles. Based on the results of the Agrochemical Soil Testing the indi-

vidual fertilization plans are elaborated for farmers (individual, cooperative, state), if they are interested.

Geographical Information System about agricultural soils which concerns the huge data base and graphical interpretations (maps) about our soils was created several years ago. The system is computerized and actively working in Soil Fertility Research Institute, Bratislava.

The monitoring of soil properties belongs to the next another activities which are very actual in connection with data collection about our soils. It comprises 248 permanent places of observations and many parameters of soil are determined. Simultaneously, some another specific monitoring systems are performed, e. g. monitoring of soils affected by Gabčíkovo Power Station on the Danube River, monitoring of soil erosion, monitoring of N_{\min} (spring time).

What about present state of Slovakian soil science conclusively? This is no self-applause when we say, that Slovak soil science has achieved the serious level of development in comparison with another developed countries. In Slovak Republic the main scientific branches of soil science are active in research and many interesting results were obtained. Too much information about our soils are helpful in practical activities which are needed in relation to soil use and its protection. Slovakian soil science has a satisfied human, technical and institutional fundament (so far) for a worthy position among those, which are ahead within the European soil science activities. But on the other hand, we are not completely satisfied.

During the past time the theoretical research was not sufficiently emphasised and lack of deep theoretical studies is visible with regard to some branches of our soil science studies. This is result of no adequate technical support and also no sufficient contacts of our experts with the highest level of the world research activities. Lack of (institutional and personal) contacts are the causes of our no sufficient participation within the international research projects, e. g. in the frame of EC countries and/or international agencies. During the latest time the fall down of financial support of research

activities is actual. This is the next aspect of our no favourable present situation.

And now, something about future. It is difficult to speak about future when we can not estimate all aspect of our future being. I believe in real perspectives of our national soil science development and everybody of us has to do best for it. The improvement in theory is the first role of our future effort. Innovation in thinking and modification in methods of working will helpful for us to be more compatible and comparable in relation to Western Europe leader countries in pedology. "We cannot change the fruit without change of root", it means, the new principles in methods (at the beginning) and the higher level of explanations (at the end) we have to achieve on the way to higher quality and more well know research activity. The higher level of data processing is needed to be achieved not only in relation to next research activities, but in our advisory activities, too. On the way to high quality and more effective activity the principles of ecological farming and land use planning have to be comprised into the soil science investigation and vice versa, as well. Higher activity of soil science has to be achieved in strategy of studies which will be comprised the national agriculture and land use.

Name und Anschrift des Verfassers:

Pavol BIELEK

Soil Fertility Research Institutue

Gagarinova 10

827 13 Bratislava

Slovak Republic

PLANT NUTRITION ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS

J.BÍŽIK

SUMMARY

Concern the public and others exists about the health, economic and resource conservation aspects of nitrate leaching and runoff of phosphates into water supplies. The largest source of nutrients entering the groundwater is from non point sources. Agriculture is the largest contributor especially of nitrogen. Best management practices such as soil analysis, timing of application and applying only nitrogen to be removed by the crop or less are being emphasized to make more efficient use of nutrient in manure and commercial fertilizer. To limit nitrogen accumulation in soil and leaching of nitrates from the economical and environmental point of view we are offering the recommendation, which takes into account the content of nutrients in soil and in plants. Special attention is devoted to the contents of inorganic forms of nitrogen (N_{in}) and potentially available or easily mineralisable nitrogen (N_{em}).

Despite many estimates (which are necessary to use in the projection of nitrogen fertilization of crops) and despite the doubts which exist due to the simplification of many complicated relations, it is necessary to express the opinion that the utilization of information of different forms of nitrogen in soil helps to approach the optimal and rational fertilization of crops and to improve more effective management of N. This is useful not only from the economical point of view but also from the view of protection of the environment, water, and food products against nitrate contamination.

There are suggested also some possibilities to decrease the risk of leaching nitrate especially important in regions within shallow groundwater level.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

In zunehmendem Maße interessiert sich die Öffentlichkeit über die Aspekte der Gesundheit und speziell über den Nitrateintrag in das Trinkwasser. Der größte Teil der Nährstoffe, die in das Grundwasser gelangen, stammt nicht von punktuellen Quellen; die Landwirtschaft kann als größter Verursacher gesehen werden, speziell bei Stickstoff. Durch wiederholte Bodenanalysen, zeitliche Verteilung der Düngermenge und der Düngerart soll eine höhere Effizienz von Mineral- und Wirtschaftsdüngern erreicht werden. Um die Nitratverluste zu minimieren, werden aus ökonomischer Sicht Empfehlungen erarbeitet, die besonders die Stickstoffgehalte in den Pflanzen wie in Böden berücksichtigen. Besondere Aufmerksamkeit wird hierbei den anorganischen Stickstoffformen und dem potentiell verfügbaren oder leicht mineralisierbaren Stickstoff gewidmet. Trotz vieler Schätzwerte, die für die Planung der Höhe der Stickstoffgaben erforderlich sind, und trotz Zweifel, die bei der Vereinfachung der komplizierten Beziehungen aufkommen, ist die Feststellung angebracht, daß die Auswertung der Informationen über die verschiedenen Stickstoffformen im Boden zu einer optimalen Anwendung von Stickstoff in der Pflanzenproduktion verhilft. Dies ist nicht allein vom ökonomischen Standpunkt vorteilhaft, sondern vor allem aus der Sicht der Reinhaltung von Wasser, Umwelt und Nahrungsmitteln. Möglichkeiten zur Verminderung des Risikos eines Nitrateintrages, speziell in Gebieten mit hohem Grundwasserstand, werden hier aufgezeigt.

S Ú H R N

Záujem verejnosti sa predovšetkým zameriava na aspekty zdravia, hospodárstva a ochrany zdrojov pred vyplavovaním nitrátov a spalovaním fosfátov do vodných zdrojov. Najväčším zdrojom živín vstupujúcich do podzemnej vody sú nebodové zdroje. Poľnohospodárstvo je najväčším producentom najmä dusíka. Využívame pôdne analýzy s cieľom umožniť časovanie aplikácie a využívanie iba dusíka, ktorý je využiteľný rastlinami,

chceme tiež, aby sa umožnilo efektívnejšie využívať živiny z maštalného hnoja a komerčných priemyselných hnojív. Aby sme obmedzovali akumuláciu dusíka v pôde a vyplavovanie nitrátov, z hľadiska ekonomického a environmentálneho ponúkame poradenstvo, ktoré zohľadňuje obsah živín v pôde a v rastlinách. Špeciálna pozornosť sa zameriava na obsah neorganických foriem dusíka (N_{in}) a potenciálne využiteľný, alebo ľahko mineralizovateľný dusík (N_{em}).

Odhliadnúc od mnohých stanovení (ktorých použitie je potrebné pri plánovaní dusíkatého hnojenia plodín) a odhliadnúc od pochybností, ktoré existujú v dôsledku simplifikácie mnohých komplikovaných vzťahov, je potrebné vysloviť názor, že využívanie informácií o rôznych formách dusíka v pôde pomáha pri výbere optimálneho a racionálneho hnojenia plodín a zabezpečovať efektívnejšie hospodárenie s N. Toto je užitočné nielen z ekonomického hľadiska, ale tiež z hľadiska ochrany životného prostredia, vodných zdrojov a potravinovej produkcie proti kontaminácii nitrátmi.

Predpokladajú sa tiež určité možnosti zníženia rizika vyplavovania nitrátov, ktoré sú obzvlášť dôležité v regiónoch s plytkou hladinou podzemnej vody.

An increasing world population will need more food products. However this goal is not be possible to achieve without adequate intensive agriculture which is both the main user and producer of nutrients in society. Use input of organic and artificial fertilizers is a highly efficient means to increase crop yield. But increased use of fertilizers and agrochemicals has created environmental problems not only in the form of eutrophication of recipient waters, but also the degradation of ground water quality. In some places this has led to toxic levels of nitrate in wells. The magnitude of this impact ultimately depends on the local climate, soil type and agricultural conditions.

There are also other sources of nutrients loading the environment such as municipal wastes. For the major rivers of the world, strong correlations exist between the number of people living in each catchment and the concentration of nitrate and the export of nitrate from these catchments (Peierls et al. 1991). However the seasonal pattern of sources and sinks of nitrogen in a field does

not usually coincide. This is one of the reasons why leaching occurs. Moreover decomposition and mineralisation of organic soil nitrogen normally occur during the non-cropping season. This is why a catchcrop is used to bind released nitrogen and residual nitrogen after harvest. Nitrogen concentrations in drainage water can be reduced sevenfold by this catch crop practice.

For these reasons are offering many ways and alternatives of solving of the optimal use of fertilizers, especially of nitrogen fertilizers. Taking into account the reduction of N input new farming systems have been developed, moving from conventional farming, to integrated farming and finally to ecological farming (Göransson, 1993). Integrated farming means using an arable system, which economizes resources. That would entail using reduced amounts of input of pesticides and fertilizers (Lower Inputs and Less-Intensive Farming). According to Jordan and Hutcheon (1993) for less intensive integrated systems one of the main management decisions includes "nutrient are based on soil and plant chemistry". Ecological farming can be defined as a self-sufficient agroecological system based on local and renewable resources.

On the other hand, the nitrogen fertilizer supply is the primary nutrient limitation for food supply and protein content. Nitrogen fertilization is highly correlated with crop yields and is a major factor in world crop production. The main problem of plant nutrition in the present time exists in management of N fertilization to achieve both an adequate yield and production of the environment. That's why this element is a main item of rational plant nutrition and of unceasing research. I'd like to point out how this problem is being solved in Slovak Republic. As in other countries, in order to reduce N-inputs the use of nitrogen fertilization is based on information regarding contents of nitrogen in the soil before fertilizing and on the contents of nutrients in green plants. In Slovak Republic most attention is devoted to cereals especially to winter wheat. With wheat it is recommended that the first application of N-fertilizing can be made before sowing (or may be omitted entirely), the second application can be done in March. The rates of N are recommended on the basis of

soil analysis of inorganic nitrogen (N-NO_3 and N-NH_4) in layer 0-0,3 m. According to the content of N_{in} the rates of N_{in} fertilizers are suggested in Table 1.

Table 1: Rates of N_{in} $\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ for winter wheat according the content of inorganic forms of nitrogen in layer 0-0,3 m before sowing and in March

Content of N_{in} in soil in $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$	Rate of N in $\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$
3 - 5	60
6 - 9	45
10 - 13	30
14 - 16	15
> 17	0

The content of N_{in} in the soil is usually more than $10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ before sowing with the maximum rate in autumn is a $40 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ N, and in many cases can be omitted. The second nitrogen fertilization, the so-called "regenerated fertilization", is usually realized at the rate $30\text{-}45 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ N. The third rate of nitrogen (the productive fertilization) is realized in the growing phase of six leaves. To calculate the amount of nitrogen, several methods are recommended. One group of methods utilize information on the content of N, P, K, Ca and Mg in green plants, the other group also includes information on the contents of inorganic forms of nitrogen in the soil.

Relatively useful results are achieved by still another method, which takes into account not only the results of plant analysis but also the content of inorganic nitrogen in the soil layer 0-0,6 m. Samples of the soil and plants are taken at the stage of six leaves growth. The data needed include: the content of N_{in} in the soil in $\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$, the amount of nitrogen taken up by plants in $\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$, the need of nitrogen in $\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ for the presumed yield, and other information such as the number plants per ha, and weather conditions. This method was tested, while being compared to others, under different soil and climatic conditions of Slovak Republic, and quite good results were achieved.

The methods which utilize only an inorganic form of nitrogen in the soil for the calculation of rates of nitrogen are often criticized. The underlying reason for doubt is fact that these forms of N are not stable in the soil, and their content during the growing season is variable due to well - known factors. From this reason, but as well as an understanding about the nature of mineralization of organic matter in the soil as a source of inorganic nitrogen, our investigation was orientated towards assessing, at least approximately, the amount of nitrogen which individual soils may release from organic compounds during the growing season.

There are many a methodological techniques determining the forms of nitrogen potentially available for plants. I would like to present one of many possibilities of solving this problem. Our idea comes out of the content of utilizing information on the content of both inorganic and easy hydrolysable nitrogen (N_{eh}) in soil.

We have tested many methods to determine N_{eh} in soil and have selected with some modification a Norwegian method by Oien, Selmer-Olsen (1980), and are now using that method. For evaluation of the amounts of N which would be taken up by plants from the soil we were able to utilize the results of long-term field experiments. The average values of accumulated nitrogen in crop yields on control plots (without fertilization) obtained over several years, show the capability of soils to release or to mineralize organic nitrogen, into available forms for plants. This value differs for individual soils.

In addition, we took into account the average content of inorganic nitrogen in spring time of over several years in the 0-0,6 m soil layer. In samples taken in the spring time, N_{eh} was determined by a modified Oien, Selmer-Olsen method. All this information was used to estimate or calculate the amount of nitrogen which a crop might take up from organic compounds after mineralization.

There is illustrated a calibrated curve for an approximate estimation of values N_o in relation to the content of easy hydrolyzable nitrogen in soil and the assumed nitrogen which the plants may take up from the soil supply without taken into account the amount of N_{in} determined in the spring. The total amount of nitrogen from the soil supply may be calculated by means of the

following equation: $N = N_{in} \cdot 9,0,6 + N_o$ where N_{in} is the content of inorganic forms of nitrogen in the soil layer 0-0,6 m before fertilization, 9 and 0,6 are coefficients, 9 for the transformation of $mg.kg^{-1}$ and 0,6 for utilization of N by plants from N_{in} , N_o is the value in $kg.ha^{-1}$ acquired by means of N_{eh} .

Despite many estimates (which are necessary to use to project the nitrogen fertilization of crops) and despite the doubts which exist because of simplification of many complicated relations, it is necessary to express the opinion that the utilization of information on different forms of nitrogen in soil helps to approach the optimal and rational fertilization of crops and to improve a more effective management of N. This is useful not only from an economical point of view but also from the point view of protection the environment, water, and food products from nitrate contamination.

We had achieved interesting results in our study of the movement and accumulation of anorganic nitrogen in soil profile. In a field experiment based on the Orthic Luvisol with two agricultural systems (low-input and organic) the accumulation of inorganic nitrogen (N_{in}) in the soil profile was evaluated. Soil was sampled in a time period spanning every two weeks from March to December in layers from 0,2 m to 1,0 m.

The course of change of N_{in} in the soil during 1992, when winter wheat was cultivated, is characterized by a reduction of N_{in} due to the uptake of N by plants and by the accumulation of N_{in} after harvest. In the period from the end June to the end of October in layer 0 - 1 m more than $100 kg N.ha^{-1}$ had accumulated. High rainfall in November and December caused the leaching of the largest part of nitrate below the 1 m soil layer. This nitrogen unable to change into organic forms is a potential source of the pollution of underground water by nitrate. Therefore is recommended that farmers cultivate "catching" intercrops to reduce the content of the soluble forms of nitrogen in the soil profile.

The content of N_{in} in the soil was also evaluated to consider the uptake of N by winter wheat and sugar beets, taking into account soil temperature and water content in the soil. The dominate factors affecting N_{in} content are as follow: crop, soil temperature, soil humidity when winter wheat is cultivated,

soil temperature, crop and soil humidity, when sugar beets are cultivated. A mathematical evaluations of the results and the equations of the model for the above mentioned factors have been calculated, which makes possible a more general and objective evaluation of N_{in} movement in the soil.

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Name und Anschrift der Verfasser:

Ján BÍZIK
Agricultural University
Tr. A. Hlinku 2
975 01 Nitra
Slovak Republic

NATURAL EDAPHIC-ECOLOGICAL CONDITIONS AND INFLUENCE OF POLLUTED AIR ON STATE OF FOREST SOILS

E. BUBLINEC and J. KUKLA

SUMMARY

The soils are very important part of forest ecosystems. They influence, to a certain extent, qualitative and quantitative composition of natural and also changed plant and animal communities. The effort of the expression of living and unliving nature unity led regularly to revealing its geobiocenological construction and ecosystem organisation. According to the Zlatník (1976) the basics of geobiocenoses is made by ecotope which is ecologically evaluated by topos (edaphotope and climatope). Identification of edaphic-ecological requirements of real living organisms and their collectives, especially plant communities, which are confronted with the characteristics of toptype.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Nahezu für die gesamte Fläche der Slowakischen Republik kann Wald als potentielle Vegetation angenommen werden. Die historische Entwicklung der Waldböden ist sehr verschieden und kann in drei Hauptperioden eingeteilt werden. Während der ersten Periode entwickelten sich die Forstökosysteme nur unter dem Einfluß der Naturkräfte. In der zweiten Periode nahmen die Aktivitäten des Menschen zu, wie Rodungen, Abbrennen, Bewirtschaftung und Änderungen des Bestandes. Anthropogene Immissionen, die in der letzten Zeit eine so entscheidende Rolle spielen, sind noch nicht so bedeutend. Bewirtschaftung kann die Bodeneigenschaften entscheidend ändern:

In dem Buchenökosystemen ist z. B. der pH-Wert eines Cambisols nach der Rodung von 5,7 auf 4,8, das heißt beinahe um eine Einheit gesunken. Die ursprüngliche Reaktion stellte sich nach zwei bis drei Jahren wieder ein. Das Auspflanzen eines Nadelwaldes kann in relativ kurzer Zeit eine ähnliche Versauerung hervorrufen. Ein Tannenwald, der auf einer Heide gepflanzt wurde, verursachte eine Senkung des pH-Wertes (H_2O) eines Cambisols von 5,3 auf 4,2 innerhalb von 30 Jahren. Auf der anderen Seite kann das sogenannte Meliorationsverfahren den pH-Wert von 4,9 auf 6,0 erhöhen, was bei einem Eschenbestand, der nach einer Buche auf einem Luvisol gepflanzt wurde, der Fall war.

Durch Immissionen verursachte Veränderungen der pedologischen Eigenschaften können gefährlich werden, da diese einen sehr hohen oder auch einen mäßig alkalischen pH-Bereich aufweisen. So können sich in den Kronen von Tannen die pH-Werte um eine bis zwei Einheiten verändern.

Während sich die pH-Werte unter Buche in einem Bereich zwischen 3,7 und 4,2 änderten, lagen die Werte unter Tanne zwischen pH 3,2 und 3,6.

In den Nadelholzbeständen ist der Säuregrad mit dem Stammzuwachs gestiegen, die Bodeneigenschaften änderten sich bei hohem Input von S, NO_x , F und Schwermetallen. Die Konzentration der Sulphationen kann von 5 bis 70 mg/l variieren, in den Tannenbeständen kann sie bis auf 200 mg/l steigen. Die höchsten Inputs liegen bei 240 kg SO_4 pro km^2 und Jahr, wobei in den Mineralboden vom Oberflächenhumus 40 bis 130 kg SO_4 pro Jahr eingedrungen sind, in die Bodenschicht unter 25 cm Tiefe nur 3 bis 40 kg SO_4 pro Jahr. So große Mengen der Schwefelionen sind in der Lage, das ökologische Gleichgewicht einer Waldbiozönose zu destabilisieren.

S Ú H R N

Lesné ekosystémy patria k potenciálnej vegetácii temer na celom území Slovenskej republiky. Táto skutočnosť sa v určitom rozsahu odráža v každej recentnej pôde. Historický vývoj lesnej pôdy je veľmi rôznorodý a môže byť rozdelený do troch hlavných časových úsekov.

Počas prvého časového úseku sa lesné ekosystémy vyvíjali iba pod vplyvom prírodných síl.

Druhý časový úsek sa spája so zvýšenými aktivitami človeka, ako sú operácie spojené s ťažbou dreva, pálenie a lesné kultúry, vrátane konverzie stanovišťa. Antropogénne imisie hrajú v poslednom čase rozhodujúcu rolu, avšak stále ešte nemajú veľký význam.

Ale metódy hospodárenia v lese môžu tiež podstatne zmeniť pôdne vlastnosti. V ekosystéme buka sa napríklad reakcia kambizeme znížila po uskutočnení ťažby z 5,72 na 4,76, t.j. približne o jednu jednotku. Primárna pôdna reakcia sa obnovila počas 2-3 rokov. Kultivácia ihličnatých stanovišť môže podobne spôsobovať stálu acidifikáciu pôdy v relatívne krátkom čase. Smrekový les vysadený do pasienka spôsobil zníženie pH H_2O z 5,27 na 4,22 počas 30 rokov. Takzvané melioračné species môžu na druhej strane zvýšiť hodnotu pH z 4,93 na 6,02, ako to bolo v prípade stanovišťa jaseňa vysadeného po hra-be na luvizemi. Nebezpečnejšie môžu byť zmeny pedo-ekologických vlastností spôsobené imisiami. Hodnoty pH zrážok v extrémnych prípadoch menia rozsah kyslosti do oblasti veľmi kyslých pôd, ale môžu mať tiež neutrálny až mierne alkalický charakter. Koruny stromov na smrekových stanovištiach môžu acidifikovať zrážky o 1-2 pH jednotky. Zatiaľ čo pH hodnoty prepadajúceho dažďa v bukovom poraste dosahujú 3,7-4,2, hodnoty zistené v smrekovom lese fluktuujú v rozsahu 3,2-3,6. Na ihličnatých stanovištiach sa hodnota pH prepadajúceho dažďa zvyšuje s rastovou mohutnosťou. Pôdne vlastnosti sa väčšinou menia v dôsledku vysokého vstupu S a NO_x , alebo F a ťažkých kovov. Koncentrácie síranových ionov v dažďovom prepade sa pohybujú v rámci 5-70 mg/l, na smrekových stanovištiach sa môžu zvýšiť na 200 mg/l.

Maximálne získané ročné hodnoty dosahovali 240 kg SO_4 na $km^2.rok^{-1}$. Do minerálnej pôdy z povrchovej vrstvy humusu preniklo 40-130 kg SO_4 na $km^2.rok^{-1}$, pod 25 cm hrubú vrstvu pôdy len 3-40 kg SO_4 na $km^2.rok^{-1}$. Takéto veľké množstvá ionov síry môžu destabilizovať stále ekologické podmienky geobiocenóz lesa.

1. EDAPHIC-ECOLOGICAL UNITS OF FOREST ECOSYSTEMS OF SLOVAK REPUBLIC

The set of permanent ecological conditions representing the permanent ecotope of locality affects the living organisms by means of an ecologically effective environment, i. e. set of ecological factors. Owing to the interaction of climatype, edaphotope and primary succession of organisms there is the permanent ecotope of locality partially changed until the relatively stable equilibrium natural state is settled after the creation of final geobiocenose. Because there is not everywhere the same starting state of climatype and edaphotope within the framework of a landscape segment, various final biocenoses arise owing to the successional process. According to Zlatník (1976) the so-called fundamental natural geobiocenoses of leading edaphic-hydric order and its suborders belong to the absolutely most developed. These macrolimax superstructure units were created on deepest skeleton-less or weakly skeleton soil and their phytocenoses contain the maximum element of competent standard belt of vegetation (in the sense E. Schmid). The other fundamental geobiocenoses belonging to the restricted, slightly restricted, slightly wetted and wetted hydric orders, i. e. subclimax (= xeric and hydric microclimax), were created in less favourable hydropedoecological conditions under the periodical or permanent shortage or the excess of the accessible water for plants. That is why their arboreous edificators have more or less lowered growth or considerably different taxonomic composition. The plant component trophic requirements of hydrically differentiated geobiocenoses predestined hereby their competence to edaphic-trophic ecological orders and interorders.

The type of geobiocen (in the sense of Zlatník, 1976) can have a various appearance at present. In addition to the well-preserved segments of fundamental geobiocenose it includes the segments of changed geobiocenoses and geobiocenoids derived from it (disclimaxes), while the created changes of ecotope have not obtained the irreversible (paraclimax) character. In fact it represents the basal ecotopical framework of the successional complex series

of the final type of natural geobiocenosis. The geobiocenoses of the leading edaphic-hydric order have been created at specific mesoclimatic conditions of a concrete forest vegetation grade (FVG), i. e. mesoclimax. Zlatník et al. (1970) do not determine FVG according to the altitude of a locality but like the hydric and trophic orders, interorders and suborders of geobiocenoses on the base of ecocenotic formulae reflecting a character of the ecological constitution of forest stand herbaceous undergrowth taxa (Zlatník et. al. 1970).

The floristic determination of vegetation grades, edaphic-hydric and edaphic-trophic ecological orders, interorders and suborders of geobiocen types is relatively well-overworked and verified in practice at present. However, it is also necessary to the limit values of ecological factors which have caused, that the bounds of the real segments of natural geobiocenoses were created.

The pH value is an integral indicator of physical - chemical properties, biological and also trophic condition of soils. The amplitudes of mean pH values presented in Table 1 refer to a 0-5 cm mineral soil layer, less frequently they reflect the active reaction of the surface humus or peat of homeostatic forest ecosystems. The following ecological amplitudes of soil pH H₂O for the floristically identifiable edaphic - trophic orders and interorders of geobiocenoses have been determined (Kukla, 1993): oligotrophic < 3,9, hemioligotrophic 3,9 - 4,9, mesotrophic 4,9 - 6,0, hemimesotrophic 5,5 - 6,0 (the active carbonates or easy soluble salts within the reach of calciphyte or halophyte roots), heminitrotrophic 6,0 - 7,2, nitrotrophic 6,0 - 7,2 (> 70 % of the soil skeleton, more humose and airy soil), hemieutrophic 7,2 - 8, 6 and eutrophic > 8,6. Each trophic order and interorder has been divided into two suborders dependent on the actual reaction of the surface humus or 0-5 cm layer of the mineral soil and the order part of the mesophyte, nitrophyte, calciphyte or halophyte root zone.

Though the soil reaction forms, as a rule, the important point of the soil environment in a close correlation with soil trophies, it is not identical with this one. We use this mean characteristic only because it suggests the trophic regulative limits of the homeostatic geobiocenotic units with a sufficient precision.

Table 1.

The differentiation of the edaphic trophic geobiocenotic units in accordance with topsoil reaction

Trophotope			Soil reaction		
Class	Subclass	Order-	Suborder	Code	pH _{H₂O}
		interorder			0.5/>5 cm
acidotrophic		oligotrophic	normal	A	<3.9
			mesooligotrophic	B/A	<3.9/<4.9
		hemi-	oligomesotrophic	A/B	3.9/4.9
Oxy-trophic		oligotrophic	oligocalditrophic	A/D	3.9/4.9/<8.6
		mesotrophic	normal	B	4.9/6.0
hemiacido-trophic			nitromesotrophic	C/B	4.9/6.0/<7.2
		hemi-	mesocalcitrrophic	B/D	5.5/6.0/<8.6
		mesotrophic	mesohalotrophic	B/E	5.5/6.0/>8.6
hemialkalo-trophic		hemi-	mesonitrotrophic	B/C	6.0/7.2
		nitrotrophic	nitrocalcitrrophic	C/D	6.0/7.2/<8.6
		nitrotrophic	normal	C	6.0/7.2
Baso-trophic			nitrohalotrophic	C/E	6.0/7.2/>8.6
		hemi-	calcitrrophic	D	7.2/8.6
alkalo-trophic		eutrophic	calcihalotrophic	D/E	7.2/8.6/>8.6
			halocalcitrrophic	E/D	>8.6
		eutrophic	halotrophic	E	salt crust

2. ATMOSPHERIC DEPOSITIONS AS AN ECOLOGICAL FACTOR

2.1 Present situation of emissions and immissions

At present (year 1992) SO₂ is the main airborne pollutant in the Slovak Republic. Its production reaches 374 000 tons per year. The greatest amount of SO₂ are emitted in the Western Slovakian Region, the smallest in the Central Slovak

Region ($143 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$). The emissions of SO_2 in the Slovak Republic (excluding the capital Bratislava) are more equable scattered in comparison with the Bohemia.

Besides SO_2 the production of solid particles which are responsible for the transport of metals and alkaline metals is high (almost 226 000 tons per year). Another 224 000 tons of other gaseous substances, mainly NO_x escape into air. Emissions from traffic reach to 200 000 tons per year. Specific emissions of solid pollutants but also of nitrogen oxides are greatest in the Eastern Slovak Republic, where they attain as many as $1000 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ in some districts.

The Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute carries out permanent measuring of air quality in 12 industrial regions and other locations. Overall 61 stations work on the territory of Slovak Republic, from which several are integrated into the European network which monitors regional background and chemistry of rainfall (UNO EMEP network).

The mean annual concentrations of SO_2 , NO_2 and dust are given in Table 2. The mean concentrations of SO_2 in industrial regions range from 30 to $80 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Background concentrations are most frequently within the range $10\text{-}20 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, these ones at Chopok peak (2025 m above sea level) are already comparable with continental background levels. The level of N-oxide concentrations in polluted locations reaches up to 60 % of the SO_2 level. At background stations NO_x concentrations are near to SO_2 concentrations.

Table 2. The average annual concentrations of SO_2 , NO_2 and dust in $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$

Monitoring Points	SO_2	NO_2	Dust
BRATISLAVA	46	27	54
Central Slovakia	56-88	17-23	77-91
East Slovakia	30-65	-	55-82
Košice - town	31	11	61
Background stations:			
Mountains	5	3	16
Lowlands	12-17	9-15	39-49

Mean annual concentrations of solid particles in industrial regions are higher than the hygienically recommended value of 40 g.m^{-3} . High amounts of dust at background stations in agricultural regions are not surprising.

The mean annual concentrations of the most important heavy metals from selected industrial regions and background stations are given in Table 3. The highest concentrations of heavy metals were found in the East-Slovakian industrial region, especially Zn and Pb. Values found out at background stations were significantly lower in comparison with industrial regions. Great attention has been also paid to ozone during the last years. Mean annual concentration of O_3 was 25 g.m^{-3} , which corresponds to Central-European background values.

Acidity of rainfall in capital of Slovak Republic Bratislava (mean pH value 4.4) and Chopok peak (pH = 4.3) corresponds to expected values for the territory of the Slovak Republic. Normal acidity of rainfall (pH 4.8-5.8) in the lowland stations of Southern and Eastern Slovakia is, despite of the use of automatic samplers, obviously the result of neutralization due to by Ca_2^+ ions washed out in the first phase of rainfall. A high content of Ca in samples confirms this conclusion.

Table 3. The average annual concentrations of heavy metals in the air (g.m^{-3})

Monitoring Points	Pb	Mn	Cu	Zn	Cd
BRATISLAVA	186	41	65	252	
Central Slovakia	127-179	47-51	39-79	130-254	2
East Slovakia	183-495	19-31	55-428	241-1450	2-3
Košice - town	233	64	65	412	2-8
Background stations:					
Mountains	22	4	14	43	0.3
Lowlands	40-53	13-26	12-90	73-93	0.9-1.8

2.2 Influence of atmospheric deposition on forest ecosystems

Deposition of pollutants was found out by monitoring and ecological studies in Slovak Republic forest ecosystems. In accordance with the principles of the European system of global monitoring of forests arranged in cooperation with UNEP we have, in Slovak Republic, all three categories of permanent long-term study plots. They are as follows:

- a) regular quadratic network of permanent monitoring plots of 8x8 km for soils and 4x4 km for healthy state of forests with an increase in density in treated or otherwise interesting regions (for example the net of 2x2 km for TANAP - High Tatras National Park). On these plots so called "a general representative survey" of forest health and quality of ecological factors is carried out,
- b) stable irregular network of forest ecological monitoring plots (TEMP) which corresponds to the second category of so called "intensive studies on permanent plots" as they were defined by the system of European monitoring,
- c) plots where investigation is carried out on the ecosystem level. These so-called ecological experimental stations (EES), which in the system of global monitoring correspond to the third category of plots, are used "special analysis of forest ecosystems".

In the next part of our paper we give information on some results obtained in long-term study of forest ecosystems. Let us look at pH values at first. Despite of a great amount of available information on precipitation acidity we have relatively little of such data, which would give us a complete picture of their annual trend in forest ecosystems. Usually there are available only data from some time sections, most frequently from summer months, that can not provide a full picture on dynamics of H^+ ions and do not allow to quantify an annual entry and consumption of hydrogen protons. There are illustrated the closed annual cycle of H^+ ions in a precipitation of open (clear-cut) area,

throughfall of adjacent beech and spruce ecosystems and water of stream running through the beech ecosystem.

During the current year the most acid precipitation in beech ecosystems were recorded in winter and spring - a relatively high pH was found in autumn. Reaction of the open space precipitation was approximately the same or slightly more acid than in the stand. Water in surface flow had pH values within the range 7-8. The situation in the spruce ecosystem was in some aspect the same and in other aspects different. In general we can say that precipitation is throughfall. Distinctive difference between the reaction of precipitation and throughfall, which occurs throughout the year was found out only in the spruce ecosystem. It is connected mainly with high enrichment of throughfall with sulphur, which can in particular case reached as many as $78 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$ (57 % of total deposition).

The results obtained suggest some important facts. Depression of spruce ecosystems throughfall, less frequently precipitation pH values was found out mainly in spring (IV.-V.). It can have a negative effect especially with regard to forest regeneration and afforestation under the parent stand. Depression of pH values can be explained by the fact, that although the solid snow precipitation are less acid in comparison with liquid one, the emissions of acid components are greatest during the winter period. Transition toward liquid precipitation is accompanied by heavy ablation and washing of acidic deposition settled on vegetative organs, therefore the acidity of solution created in such a way also considerably increases.

The fact that throughfall acidity copy the course of the precipitation acidity is important too. It suggests distinctive exogenous effect. Differences are caused by interaction of precipitation with tree species vegetative organs, i.e. by so called leaching of various substances from assimilation organs. It is also interesting that time dynamics of the changes of precipitation acidity is also partially reflected with some shift of pH values in stream water. The increase of whole concentration of elements in throughfall is caused mainly by washing of pollutants settled on vegetative organs of plants. This fact can be supported by data on annual dynamics of sulphate anions and also other ele-

ments in throughfall, which also copy the course of their concentrations on the precipitation. It is valid for beech as also for spruce ecosystem.

From practical and theoretical viewpoint it is important that acidity of throughfall was increased with stocking, it means with rise of stand density. The most acidic precipitation were found out in stands with highest stocking. The pH values measured under surface humus confirmed this fact. Also soil solutions caught in the 10 cm depth of mineral soil exhibit slightly similar trend. In the depth of 25 cm this phenomenon disappears.

Annual entries of selected elements into Slovak mountain forest ecosystems (H^+ , $N:NO_3^-$, $N:NH_4^+$, P , K^+ , Ca_2^+ , Mg_2^+ , $S:SO_4^{2-}$ and Na^+) range from 90 to 100 $kg\cdot ha^{-1}$ (total deposition). This amounts are valid for territories with remote transport of imissions (regional pollution). In lowlands and partially polluted regions these entries are of higher orders. Enrichment of precipitation in the tree crowns makes 30-40 $kg\cdot ha^{-1}\cdot yr^{-1}$, it means that 130-140 $kg\cdot ha^{-1}\cdot yr^{-1}$ of given elements reach the soil surface in forest ecosystems. Sulphur has the greatest share from the elements entering ecosystems (30-50 $kg\cdot ha^{-1}\cdot yr^{-1}$, in average 42 %). While in deciduous forests the amount of S does not change after penetrating of precipitation through stand canopy ($\pm 30 kg\cdot ha^{-1}\cdot yr^{-1}$) and percentage of S even drops (from 30 % to 24 %), in coniferous ecosystems on the other hand increases to 80-100 $kg\cdot ha^{-1}\cdot yr^{-1}$, i.e. to 55-60%. Precipitation penetrating through the canopy of deciduous stand are enriched considerably with K^+ and relatively also with P, in the case of coniferous stands with S, H^+ and Ca_2^+ ions. Ratio of deposition of acid and alkalic components in precipitation is usually 170:110, while in throughfall of deciduous ecosystems makes 85:100. It changes in favour of basic components. Analogous coefficients in coniferous stands are 115:100 and 280:100 and ratio is changed markedly in favour of acid components.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Soils and their properties form the basis of the stability of forest ecosystems. The knowledge of a such key links enables us to determine, in advance, also the direction of their further development. On this base can by made preventive measures for improving of and regulation of forest stands.

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Name und Anschrift der Verfasser:

Eduard BUBLINEC und Ján KUKLA
Sciences and Technical University
Štúrova 2
960 53 Zvolen
Slovak Republic

NATURAL AND MAN-INDUCED FACTORS OF SOIL POLLUTION (AND HYGIENE)

J.ČURLÍK and L.MATÚŠKOVÁ

SUMMARY

Soil contamination is one of the soil degradation processes that include considerable number of cooperating factors, either natural, or anthropogenic origin. Soil contamination in Slovak Republic partially has its origin in natural (geochemical), but particularly in the changes caused by man. Landscape that from geochemical point of view is very complex, has relatively abundant occurrence of hydrochemically changed and mineralised minerals, this is possible to see in the soils of geochemically anomalous zones. These are occurring in volcanic and some crystalline regions. Soils in this regions can be more rich in Hg, Zn, Cu, Cd, Pb and As (Centralslovakian volcanic bows, Spišsko-gemerské Rudohorie). On the other hand however, there is overwhelming contamination from the industries, mining, urbanism and agriculture with not beneficial changes in abiotic soil processes. In Slovak Republic there are some regions "hot spots" with specific soil pollutants that are depending from the type of industrial sources. To the group of most contaminated regions belong:

Žiar nad Hronom (aluminium plant) with heavy metals and fluorine;

Krompachy-Rudňany (metallurgy) with Hg and heavy metals;

Jelšava-Lubeník (magnetite plant) with Mg and heavy metals;

Low Orava (metallurgy, alloy production) with Cr and heavy metals.

Remaining regions are much less contaminated:

Bratislava with heavy metals and some organic pollutants;

Upper Nitra (chemical industry, power plant) with heavy metals ;

Strážske-Humenné (chemical industry) with some organic pollutants and PCBs;

Equally with newest estimate about 100 000 ha farming land and 180 000 ha forest land in Slovak Republic are contaminated in various rate. It was announced, that some farming land has increased values of its contamination, although under acceptable limit, due to fertilization (Cd, Hg).

As far as organic pollutant contents is concerned, present level of knowledge is limited. They are based on preliminary results from:

a) Slovak Republic experimental regions;

b) some regional locations of sampling.

Some sites of soil contamination occurred close to the sources (some chemical plant). At present is not know their spatial distribution. Another risk for soil is acidity (dry and moist heap). Relatively great Slovak Republic regions (identical with "hot spots", but larger) are under impact of acidification processes. These processes can contribute to element leaching (metals) with undesired changes in the processes of biological transformation.

In order to understand present soil contamination status, several research activities in the Soil Fertility Research Institute, Bratislava are focused to these topics: Slovak Republic soil geochemical atlas, soil contamination with PCBs, etc. These projects results are promising better contamination processes understanding. It is obvious that soils in Slovak Republic are much less polluted, than it used to be referred.

In order to have possibility to check soil contamination status and soil hygiene, in Slovak Republic we have accepted Holland ABC limits, as well as soil conservation act.

The Soil Fertility Research Institute was declared for monitoring and information centre of soil hygiene, this is the part of information system on Slovak Republic environment.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Bodenverschmutzung ist ein Prozess der Bodendegradation, der durch eine Reihe von natürlichen und menschlichen Faktoren ausgelöst wird.

Die Bodenverschmutzung in der Slowakei stammt teilweise von natürlichen (geochemischen), aber am meisten von den Einflüssen menschlichen Ursprungs. Wie in einem Lande mit einer komplizierten Geologie treten hydrothermal veränderte und mineralisierte Gesteine hervor und man kann (auch) geochemisch anomale Zonen beobachten, so in vulkanischen und manchen kristallinen Gebieten. Die Böden können in Regionen mit Hg, Zn, Cu, Cd, Pb und As angereichert werden (der Mittelslowakische vulkanische Bogen, Spišsko-gemerské rudohorie Gebirge). Andererseits sind die Verschmutzungen, verursacht durch die Industrie, den Bergbau die Stadtentwicklung und die Landwirtschaft zu nennen.

In der Slowakei werden mehrere sehr verschmutzte Regionen mit spezifischen Bodenverunreinigungen, in Abhängigkeit von der Art der Industrie. Zu der Gruppe der meistverschmutzten Regionen gehört:

Žiar nad Hronom (Aluminiumwerke) mit den Schwermetallen und Fluor,
Krompachy-Rudňany (Schmelzhütte) mit Hg und Schwermetallen,
Jelšava-Lubeník (Magnesitwerke) mit Mg und Schwermetallen,
Dolná Orava (Schmelzhütten und Legierungen) mit Cr und Schwermetallen.

Andere Regionen sind viel weniger verunreinigt: Bratislava mit den Schwermetallen und manchen organischen Verunreinigungen,

Horná Nitra (Chemische Industrie, Elektrizitätswerke) mit den Schwermetallen und As,

Košice (Stahlwerke) mit Schwermetallen,

Strážske-Humenné (Chemische Industrie) mit manchen organischen Verunreinigungen und PCBs.

In der Übereinstimmung mit der letzten Schätzung sind um 100 Tausend Hektar von landwirtschaftlichen und 180 Tausend Hektar von Waldböden in der Slowakei in verschiedener Stufe kontaminiert. Zunehmende Werte, obwohl

unter der Grenze wurden von den landwirtschaftlichen Böden als Konsequenz der Verfrachtung durch Wind angegeben (Cd, Hg). Was die organische Verunreinigungen betrifft, sind die gegenwärtigen Kenntnisse sehr begrenzt. Sie beruhen an vorläufigen Resultaten von

- a) Versuchsregionen in der Slowakei,
- b) von manchen regionalen Probepunkten.

Manche Bodenverunreinigungen wurden in der engsten Nähe der Erreger (chemische Werke) gefunden. Die flächenhafte Verteilung ist derzeit noch nicht bekannt. Ein anderes Risiko für den Boden ist eine saure Belastung (trockene und nasse Ablagerung). Relativ große Gebiete in der Slowakei (identisch mit den "heißen Flecken", aber mehr ausgedehnt) sind unter dem Einfluß der Säurebildungsprozesse. Diese Prozesse können das Auslaugen von Elementen (Metallen) mit unerwünschten Veränderungen in den Prozessen der biologischen Transformation verursachen.

Um den gegenwärtigen Zustand der Bodenverunreinigung zu verstehen, sind einige Forschungsaktivitäten des Forschungsinstitutes für Bodenfruchtbarkeit in Bratislava diesem Problem gewidmet: Geochemischer Atlas der slowakischen Böden, Monitoring System der Slowakei, Bodenverunreinigung mit PCBs u.a. Erkenntnisse aus diesen Projekten sollen zum besseren Verstehen der Verunreinigungsprobleme beitragen. Es ist klar, daß die Böden in der Slowakei weniger verunreinigt sind als berichtet wurde. Um die Kontrolle des Bodenverunreinigungszustandes und der Bodenhygiene zu ermöglichen, würden die holländischen ABS-Beschränkungen in der Slowakei mit dem Bodenschutzgesetz übernommen.

Das Forschungsinstitut für Bodenfruchtbarkeit wurde als Monitoring - und Informationszentrum für Bodenhygiene erklärt, das ein Teil des Umweltinformationssystems in der Slowakei ist.

SÚHRN

Pôdna kontaminácia je jedným z procesov znehodnotenia pôdy, ktoré zahŕňajú značný počet spolupôsobiacich faktorov, tak prírodného, ako aj ľudského pôvodu. Kontaminácia pôdy na Slovensku má svoj pôvod čiastočne v prírodných (geochemických), ale najmä v človekom spôsobených zmenách. Ako krajina, ktorá je z geologického hľadiska veľmi zložitá má pomerne hojný výskyt hydrotermicky zmenených a mineralizovaných nerastov a možno pozorovať v pôdach geochemicky anomálne zóny. Tieto sa vyskytujú vo vulkanických a niektorých kryštálických oblastiach. Pôdy v týchto regiónoch môžu byť bohatšie na Hg, Zn, Cu, Cd, Pb a As (Stredoslovenské vulkanické oblúky, Spišsko-gemerské Rudohorie). Na druhej strane však prevláda kontaminácia z priemyslu, baníctva, urbanizmu a poľnohospodárstva s nepriaznivými zmenami v abiotických pôdnych procesoch. Na Slovensku sú niektoré regióny "hot spots" so špecifickými pôdnymi polutantmi, ktoré závisia od typu priemyselných zdrojov. Do skupiny najviac kontaminovaných regiónov patria:

Žiar nad Hronom (závody na výrobu hliníka) s ťažkými kovmi a fluórom,

Krompachy-Rudňany (huty) s Hg a ťažkými kovmi,

Jelšava-Lubeník (magnezitový závod) s Mg a ťažkými kovmi,

Dolná Orava (huty a výroba zliatín) s Cr a ťažkými kovmi.

Ostatné regióny sú oveľa menej kontaminované:

Bratislava s ťažkými kovmi a niektorými organickými polutantmi,

Horná Nitra (chemický priemysel, elektrárň) s ťažkými kovmi a As,

Košice (železiarne) s ťažkými kovmi,

Strážske-Humenné (chemický priemysel) s niektorými organickými polutantmi a PCBs.

Zhodne s najnovším odhadom okolo 100.000 ha poľnohospodárskych pôd a okolo 180.000 ha lesných pôd na Slovensku je v rôznom stupni kontaminovaných. Bolo referované, že niektoré poľnohospodárske pôdy majú zvýšené hodnoty, aj keď pod prípustnou hranicou, ako dôsledok hnojenia (Cd, Hg).

Čo sa týka organických polutantov je súčasný stav poznania veľmi obmedzený. Je založený na predbežných výsledkoch z:

- a) pokusných regiónov na Slovensku
- b) niektorých regionálnych miest vzoriek.

Niektoré miesta pôdnej kontaminácie sa vyskytovali v bezprostrednej blízkosti zdrojov (niektoré chemické závody). V súčasnosti nie je známe priestorové rozdelenie.

Iným rizikom pre pôdu je kyslosť (suchá a mokrá skládka). Pomerne veľké oblasti na Slovensku (identické s "hot spots", ale rozsiahlejšie) sú pod vplyvom acidifikačných procesov. Tieto procesy môžu prispieť k vyluhovaniu prvkov (kovov) s neželanými zmenami v procesoch biologickej transformácie.

Aby sme chápali súčasný stav pôdnej kontaminácie, niekoľko výskumných aktivít Výskumného ústavu pôdnej úrodnosti v Bratislave je venovaných tomuto problému: Geochemický atlas slovenských pôd, monitorovací systém Slovenska, pôdna kontaminácia s PCBs a ďalšie. Výsledok týchto projektov sľubuje lepšie pochopenie problémov znečistenia. Je zrejmé, že pôdy na Slovensku sú oveľa menej znečistené než sa o tom referovalo.

Aby sme mali možnosť kontroly stavu pôdnej kontaminácie a pôdnej hygieny, prevzali sa na Slovensku holandské limity ABC i zákon na ochranu pôdy. Výskumný ústav pôdnej úrodnosti bol vyhlásený za monitorovacie a informačné centrum pôdnej hygieny, čo je časť informačného systému o životnom prostredí na Slovensku.

INTRODUCTION

The principal factors that dictate the chemical composition of soil is the composition of parent material. The enrichment or depletion of chemical elements in the soil profiles depends on relative mobility of the elements under weathering condition. The distribution of the chemical elements in soil profiles is controlled by pedogenic processes in conjunction with elemental cycling by plants. Soils under natural conditions may contain the concentra-

tions of some metals at phytotoxic levels. Such elevated concentrations of many heavy metals in Slovakian soils correspond to geochemically anomalous zones which represent some parent rocks (basic and ultrabasic), mineralized zones and secondary dispersion fields around these bodies. Anthropogenic inputs of the pollutants (inorganic-organic) are major sources of pollution in soils. Fig.1, which schematically indicates various sources of pollutants in soils points to more diverse and complex inputs in comparison to natural pollution. The composition, concentration and mode of occurrence of the pollutants vary widely and may influence their behaviour in soils. Principally all sources of soil pollution can be point- and non-point sources. Soil contamination in Slovak Republic has geographical, technological and political causes: The development of heavy industry after second world war and implementation of non-proper technology, led to the gradual increase of pollutants in the environmental constituents. Although, heavy metals have been put to the soils of some mining areas for centuries, their substantial increasing occur with the rising industrialization. One of the main sources of pollutants in soils is polluted atmosphere.

Fig.1: Diverse sources of anthropogenic and natural inputs of metals into soils.

SLOVAK ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY DEVELOPMENT SOIL POLLUTION

From environmental studies is clear that different chemicals end up in the soils and sediment and may cause the pollution problems. Such soil pollution is mostly irreversible. Since we desire that soil have to retain their multi-functional potential for use, the environmental risk philosophy for soils has to be developed.

Slovak environmental policy is not clustered in themes (acidification, eutrophication..) but rather in target groups (agriculture, transport, industry...) and environmental constituents groups (air, water, soils, food chain). There is no government policy project on ecological sustainability in Slovak Republic. But several concepts and conceptual models are elaborated (Green concept, EIA..). This clustering caused some responsibility problems. Ministry of Agriculture is responsible for soil protection while the other environmental constituents groups (air, water) are guided by Ministry of Environment.

Within the law on Soil protection the target values or permissible levels for risk elements in soils were legalized (Decision, 1994). For this purpose the Dutch ABC-list (1991) was adopted. To do so, several reasons has been taken into account:

- a) reference values represent negligible ecotoxicological risk
- b) most comprehensive list of inorganic and organic pollutants
- c) integrated quality standards for air, water and soils (IQS-AWS) were adopted.

Some parameters relevant to heavy metals pollution

The toxic effect of the heavy metals and their availability for microorganisms, plants, animals and human-beings, depends on many factors. Mostly on the solubility, mode of occurrence in soils, concentration and others. Some elements which are essential for the living organisms, over certain range of concentration can be harmful or even "toxic" for the same organisms.

Soil is a complex medium consisting of primary and secondary minerals, organic matter and organisms, water and air. This body is capable to trap

and accumulate many elements of natural or technogenic origin. These are immobile in soils unless they are chemically or biologically altered or enter the aqueous phase. The main mechanisms which determine the mobility of the chemical elements are: cation exchange, precipitation (coprecipitation), adsorption, bio-adsorption. The immobilisation of the chemical elements is caused by such contributing factors as pH, redox-potential, carbonates-, humus- and clay content.

For better understanding the possible adverse effect of these heavy metals, the following parameters are useful:

- a) "Total (bulk) content" - the total quantity of the various elements which depends on determination procedure. This is understood by the tradition in different countries, the amount of extractable fraction of the elements in nitro-hydrochloric acid (queen water), in 2M (1M) HNO_3 and others. In Slovak Republic special methods of sample preparation, extraction (decomposition), and analytical procedure for the different groups of the elements are recommended to assure the determination of the bulk content (Decision..., 1994)
- b) "Soluble content" is highly solute - specific. The amount of "soluble" fraction depends on mode of element occurrence in the soils and shows a great variability depending on the influencing factors. In Slovak Republic the extraction with 2M HNO_3 was used. This extractant is too strong. Some other extractants are recommended at present (EDTA, ammonium acetate, citric acid and oth.)
- c) "Mobile fraction"- a portion from the bulk content which can be transported, or can migrate to the plants or to the groundwater. This is highly variable and time (space) dependent content. It can be determined by analysing of soil water.

Only "mobile forms" of the elements are "available" for the plants. Immobile forms are not available and have no adverse effect to the plants, animals, and human-beings.

Conventionally ecotoxicological risk assessment for soils dealt with the "bio-available" fraction of chemicals. It is known however that we must not ignore fraction immobilized in sediment and soils. This fraction can cause the non-linear time delayed responses (chemical time bomb). In addition to this it is necessary to examine vertical transport of the pollutants along the soil profile.

Soil pollution and soil degradation

The presence of certain chemical elements or compounds in soils at levels that would have detrious effects can be considered as a soil pollution. This broad statement needs the explanation in a sense that three categories of harmful effects are included (Mattigod and Page, 1983):

- a) the pollutants would diminish soil fertility
- b) the pollutants may not affect the growth of vegetation but would constitute the threat to higher organisms by consuming the plants
- c) the pollutants may adversely affect beneficial use of the groundwater due to recharge of constituents from the soils.

Therefore the term of soil pollution encompasses all categories of harmful effects.

The FAO (1979) defined soil degradation as "a process which lowers the current and/or the potential capability of soil to produce (quantitatively an/or qualitatively) goods or services".

Soil degradation is connected with the physical, chemical and biological changes in soils. Involves natural and man-induced contributing factors.

While physical and chemical degradation is influenced by natural as well as man-induced factors, biological degradation is almost entirely caused by man activity. Biological degradation includes undesirable changes in microbial population, changes in microbial and faunal activity including biological transformation processes (Váralyay, 1986). Biological degradation and degradation due to changing of buffering capacity of soils are very closely inter-relating processes (related to the soil pollution):

This schema shows that soil pollution is one of the very important contributing factors of soil degradation. That is why some authors place the increase in toxic elements in soils among the soil degradation process (Smal and Salomon, 1991)

Present knowledge on soil pollution

To state that soils are contaminated, some knowledge is needed on so called "background levels" for the different soil units or soil regions. In Slovak Republic several sources of information are available:

- a) research of the state of soil pollution in the most industrialized regions. This was based mostly on the results obtained from the analyses so called "soluble" fraction of soils (extraction by 2M HNO₃ or 1M HCl) (Kalúz, 1992, FIALA et al., 1991, ČURLÍK, FIALA, DLAPA, 1992 and oth.). Soils were sampled in the grids, mostly from the humus horizons in the surroundings of supposed sources of contaminations (plants, electro-power stations)
- b) soil monitoring has started some years ago. In the frame of this project the pollution problem has been tackled. Unfortunately the same analytical methods (extraction with 2M HNO₃) has been applied.
- c) agrochemical soil testing which is already done in several cycles for agricultural soils and was oriented on ascertaining the "available"

nutrients (N, P, K), pH, carbonate status was extended for some heavy metals (Cr, Cd, Hg, Pb). Again "extractable" forms were analysed.

- d) geochemical mapping of soil in Slovak Republic started in 1991. Within this project agricultural and forest soils are sampled over all territory (1 sample/ 10 km²) from The A and C horizons. Bulk content of the assemblage of 36 chemical elements has been analysed. This project will end in 1995 and will form a good basis for the detailed studies
- e) no systematic study of the organic pollutants is provided. Some results were obtained from: 6 pilot regions in Slovak Republic, monitoring of PCBs around the supposed point sources of contamination and more informations were obtained from Danube lowland. At present more attention is paid to PCB, PAU, and pesticide residues extension in Slovakian soils and to the study of the transport mechanisms of the organic pollutants from the soils to the plants.

Some other sources -mostly geochemical are also available.

Soil prospecting methods were widely used in geological survey.

The obtained results showed that it is possible to the certain level distinguish geochemical and technogenic anomalies and approach the "background levels".

Metal concentration under natural conditions

Geochemical studies indicate the relationship that exists between the metal content in parent rocks and soils. Some basic and ultrabasic rocks have higher content of Cr, Mn, Zn, Cu, Cd, Co, Ni.

Enrichment of metallic elements was observed in the soils on gabros, serpentinites and oth. Typical ranges of metal concentrations found in soils are illustrated in Fig.2, were taken from Bowen (1979, Cit.: Mattigod and Page, 1983).

Elevated concentrations of Cu, Hg, Zn, Pb have been find by the soil prospecting in the volcanic region of the middle Slovak Republic, where are due

to ore bodies or due to secondary dispersion. Secondary dispersions is difficult to detect because they are overlapped by the old hips, tailings which are having very old history in Slovak Republic.

Fig. 2: Ranges and median values of metal concentrations found in uncontaminated soils (data from Bowen, 1979).

Hot spots areas

The ecologically most endangered areas (hot spots) are distributed around the industrial centres to them belong: Middle Spiš region (Krompachy, Rudňany), Žiar n/Hronom region, Jelšava -Lubeník, Hačava-Hnúšťa, and Lower Orava region. Upper Nitra, Ružomberok, Košice, Strážske -Humenné-Vranov and Vojany regions are far less polluted.

Middle Spiš region is a common name for the immision areas of Metal works of Krompachy town and Iron ores mines at Rudňany. Both immision areas

are overlapped. At Krompachy the metal works has imitted in 1986 y. 19838 t of SO₂, 1383 t of dust and 92 t of As. This situation has radically changed after the substantial technological improvement and sinked at about 50%. Heavy metals (Cu, Hg, Ni, Cd, Pb and Zn) are present in the imitted dust. The acreage of the contaminated agricultural soils is about 11000 ha.

At Rudňany the most dangerous problem was the mercury production. Mercury was spread in the surroundings and is present in the soils, stream sediment and in the water. The acreage of polluted soils is not accurately known but it may be several thousands ha. Alumina works at Žiar n/Hronom produce specific pollutant fluorine (together with Hg, As). The estimation of the water soluble F showed that about 3700 ha have concentrations above the limit (10 mg/kg of water soluble F). The substantial improvement is supposed in 1995, when the new technology will be applied.

Two another very specific regions (Hačava-Hnúšťa, Jelšava-Lubeník) are polluted by Mg from magnezite works, together with some heavy metals. Enormous amount of dust sedimented in the soils and the crusts of secondary Mg minerals were formed in the topsoil. In the Hačava-Hnúšťa about 3000 ha and at Jelšava-Lubeník about 18000 ha of soils are to the different levels contaminated (alkalized).

Dolná Orava region known by ferro-alloys factories (Istebné) in which about 13 different alloys were produced. At present the new technology is applied but in the past Cr and Mn polluted about 13000 ha of soils.

In the region of Horná Nitra As and Hg are the main pollutants around the chemical factories and electric-power station. At Košice (iron works) some heavy metals and dust, at Vojany (electric-power station) As. In all mentioned regions SO₂ is another important pollutant. At Ružomberok SO₂ is the main problem but the soils are only slightly polluted by heavy metals.

In all regions not-points sources of contamination operate. Based on the available data in Slovak Republic about 180 000 ha of soils are to the different level polluted. The new recommendations for the use and assanation of such soils were elaborated at present.

Organic pollutants

No systematic aerial studies of organic pollutants were carried out in Slovak Republic. Some non-systematic studies has provided us with some preliminary results. These show that soil contamination by organic pollutants (PCBs) does not form any significant aerial pollution problem. Point sources of contamination represent some chemical factories (Strážske-Humenné) in which organic compounds are produced or used.

Some conclusion remarks

Over past decade soil contamination has emerged as a key environmental issue. The sources of contamination are very diverse in Slovak Republic. It has technological, geographical, historical and even political causes. Industrialization in conjunction with wastes technology and heavy industry are the main of them.

To deal with the problem of contaminated soils we must include contaminated levels and the effect to plants (food chain) and to the other environmental constituents (integrated approach).

It is necessary to deal with soil as with multi-functional ecological component that is critical to sustaining the current and future environmental quality.

Soil quality must possess no harm to human, plants or animal, not adversely affect natural cycles or functions and not contaminate other environmental constituents.

Among other pollutants heavy metals are the most spread in Slovakian soils and so, critical concentrations of heavy metals in soils (in relation to microorganisms, plants, surface and groundwater protection) should be understood. To assess the risk chemical elements and compounds the Dutch ABC- list was adopted.

New data are needed to ascertain the different classes of polluted soils in hot spots regions in Slovak Republic to propose further land use and take proper measures for assanation.

Further research has to be concentrated on the modelling of behaviour and leaching of metals in the soils with regard to uptake by plants and to groundwater quality.

Risk assessment of predicted concentration of metals in the soils, groundwater and sediment should be carried out.

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Name und Anschrift der Verfasser:

Ján ČURLÍK; Libuška MATÚŠKOVÁ

Soil Fertility Research Institute

Gagarinova 10

827 13 Bratislava

Slovak Republic

SOIL UNITS AND THEIR DISTRIBUTION IN THE AGRICULTURAL AREA OF LOWER AUSTRIA

O.DANNEBERG, I.POVOLNY, H.GOTTSCHLING and O.NESTROY

SUMMARY:

A soil Quality Network Program (Bodenzustandsinventur) concerning all the land in agricultural use has recently been completed in Lower Austria. This program provides a reliable basis for the determination of soil units and the estimation of their area distribution.

In this program a basic network of soil sampling points with a distance of 3,9 km was established. This was densened by additional sampling points, thus resulting in a final network with a point-to-point distance of 2,76 km. Basic points were sampled to several depths, additional points only for 0 - 20 cm. The soil-profiles of all points were pedologically evaluated and classified. The total program resulted in 1449 sampling points, which represent a total area of 966,954 ha; thus, as an average, one point represents an area of 667 ha. The soil types of these sampling points were dropped in to a scheme of 29 typological units according to the Austrian System of Soil Classification. Also, the geological substrates of soil formation were grouped into a scheme: by chance, there were also 29 substrata units.

A combination of these two principals of classification was desirable, however not practicable in every case. To succeed in the determination of soil units of the kind "soil type on soil forming substrata" we decided to use one of the two principals, i.e. the typological unit, in every case; the other principale, however, was used for a further subdivision only if there were enough points for a successful statistical analysis of the data. Thus, we arrived at a total of

63 soil units in Lower Austria. The areas of these units are estimated, the respective data are presented. The local distribution of these units are presented in maps.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Eine abgeschlossene Bodenzustandsinventur, die die landwirtschaftlich genutzte Bodenfläche Niederösterreichs betrifft, bietet eine verlässliche Grundlage zur Formulierung von Bodeneinheiten und zur Abschätzung der jeweiligen Flächenanteile. Das Meßprogramm beruht auf einem flächendeckenden Raster von Meßpunkten. Im Basisraster beträgt der Abstand von Punkt zu Punkt 3,9 km. Durch Zusatzrasterpunkte wurde systematisch im Verhältnis 1:1 verdichtet und so der Punkteabstand auf 2,76 km vermindert. Basisrasterpunkte wurden nach mehreren Tiefenstufen, Zusatzrasterpunkte auf 0 - 20 cm beprobt. Die Bodenprofile aller Punkte wurden bodenkundlich angesprochen und klassifiziert. Das gesamte Programm umfaßte 1449 Meßpunkte, die einer landwirtschaftlichen Nutzfläche von 966,954 ha entsprechen; ein Punkt entspricht damit einer Fläche von 667 ha.

Die Bodentypen dieser Meßpunkte wurden in ein Schema mit 29 bodentypologischen Einheiten eingeordnet, Grundlage war das Österreichische Bodentypenschema. Ebenso wurden die bodenbildenden geologischen Substrate in ein Schema geordnet, zufällig ergaben sich hier ebenfalls 29 Einheiten. Eine einfache Kombination dieser beiden Einteilungsprinzipien erschien wünschenswert, war aber nicht in jedem Einzelfall durchführbar. Um zu praktikablen Bodeneinheiten der Kombination "Bodentyp auf bodenbildendem Substrat" zu kommen, wurde daher ein hierarchisches Schema benützt: Eines der beiden einteilenden Prinzipien, und zwar die Bodentypologie, wurde in jedem Fall angewandt, das zweite jedoch nur dann, wenn die Anzahl an Meßpunkten eine weitere Unterteilung erlaubte. Das so entstehende Schema weist 63 Einheiten (bzw. Untereinheiten) auf. Ihre Flächenanteile wurden abgeschätzt, ihre räumliche Verteilung wird in Karten dargestellt.

SÚHRN

Uzavretá inventúra pôdy, ktorá sa zameriava na poľnohospodársky využívané pozemky, poskytuje dostatočnú základňu pre tvorbu pôdnych jednotiek a hodnotenie ich plošného zastúpenia. Program hodnotenia spočíva v celoplošnej mriežke, ktorá obsahuje odmerné body. V základnej mriežke vzdialenosť medzi jednotlivými bodmi je 3,9 km. Vložením dodatočných bodov sa tento vyťah systematicky zahusťuje na pomer 1 : 1 a vzájomná vzdialenosť sa znižuje na 2,76 km. Základné body mriežky majú niekoľko odberových hĺbok, dodatočné body iba hĺbku 0 - 20cm. Pôdne profily všetkých bodov boli pôdnoznameckým spôsobom klasifikované. Celý program obsahuje 1449 bodov odberu, ktoré zodpovedajú ploche poľnohospodársky využívanej pôdy 966 954 ha; jeden odmerný bod takto charakterizuje plochu 667 ha.

Pôdne typy týchto merných bodov boli podľa schémy usporiadané do 29 pôdnych typologických jednotiek, podľa rakúskej schémy pôdnych typov. Podobne boli rozstriedené pôdotvorné geologické substráty, náhodou to tiež bolo 29 jednotiek. Jednoduchá kombinácia oboch týchto princípov delenia sa ukázala byť žiadúca, ale nebolo možné ju aplikovať v každom jednotlivom prípade. Aby sme mohli vytvoriť použiteľné kombinované jednotky pôdny typ na pôdotvornom substráte, použili sme hierarchickú schému, založenú na oboch klasifikačných princípoch a tým tiež pôdnu typológiu v každom z klasifikovaných bodov, druhý z princípov sa aplikoval iba tam, kde počet odberných bodov umožňoval ďalšie delenie. takto vzniknutá schéma vykazuje 63 jednotiek (čiže podradov). Bude sa hodnotiť ich plošné zastúpenie, ich priestorové rozdelenie sa potom nanesie na mapu.

INTRODUCTION

A soil quality network program concerning all the land in agricultural use has recently been completed in Lower Austria (BUNDESANSTALT FÜR BODENWIRTSCHAFT, 1994). This program will provide a reliable basis for the formulation of soil units and the estimation of their area distribution. The results of

this network program are especially valuable, since another possible basis for the formulation of soil units, the Austrian Soil Survey, (KRABICHLER; 1984; DANNEBERG, 1986), is not yet fully available for this purpose. The Austria Soil Survey has already collected the data of 95 % of the agriculturally used land of Austria. However, especially in Lower Austria, some important districts are still missing. Furthermore, all the data collected are available only in a classic form and up to now we have no modern computer-system to evaluate these data and to produce aggregated soil units. Thus the results of the soil quality network program are very welcome at this time to give a general view on the soils in the agricultural area of Lower Austria.

FEATURES OF SOIL QUALITY NETWORK PROGRAMS:

The aim of these programs is to show the quality of the soils of a larger area, for example of a province of Austria at a respective time: the main point is the state of contamination of soils, especially with heavy metals. The programs use regular network of sampling points, completely covering the area to be investigated the distance of sampling points in the basic network is 3,9 km. The network can be and should be densened, either systematically or at places of special interest.

At the sampling points, soil samples are withdrawn for analysis. The samples are taken from soil layers with defined depths and not from diagnostic soil horizons. For arable land samples are taken from 0 - 20 cm, 20 - 40 cm, 40 - 50 cm, >50 cm: for grassland the respective depths are 0 - 5 cm, 5 - 10 cm, 10 - 20 cm, 20 - 40 cm, 40 - 50 cm, >50 cm. Together with sampling, a pedological evaluation and classification of the site is carried out; also, the sites are related to the Austrian Soil Survey. The soil samples thus obtained are analysed for particle size distribution, pH, total-N, humus, carbonate exchangeable cations, CEC and "total contents" (= soluble in Aqua regia) of nutrient and detrimental elements. The list of parameters to be analysed can be enlarged in cases of interest, for example for organic contaminants.

All these and other features of soil quality network programs have been discussed by a working group of the Austrian Soil Science Society and published by BLUM et al. (1989).

NETWORK OF SAMPLING POINTS IN LOWER AUSTRIA:

In Lower Austria the basic network of sampling points was systematically densened 1:1, thus resulting at a final point-to-point distance of 2.76 km. The total program comprises a sum of 1,449 sampling points, 725 of which are basic points, while 724 are additional points. Basic points were fully sampled in the way described above, additional points, however, were sampled only for 0 - 20 cm. 576 basic points and 575 additional points are situated on arable land, 149 basic and 149 additional point on grassland. Map Nr. 1 (in the appendix of this paper) shows the network of sampling points in Lower Austria.

These 1,449 points represent a statistical sample of all the soils present in their agricultural land of Lower Austria. This land makes up a total area of 966,954 ha; as published by agricultural statistics (NÖ - LANDESLAND-WIRTSCHAFTSKAMMER; 1992). The probability of any soil unit to appear in the sample is only dependent on the area occupied by this unit, a double area will also result in a doubled number of points in the sample. Thus, as an average, one point represents 667 ha. Multiplying the number of points of any kind of unit by this figure will result in an estimate of the area occupied by the respective unit; the error of estimation will be the lower, the higher the number of points within the respective unit.

PRINCIPLES OF GROUPING OF THE DATA:

The total material of data can be grouped according to different principles. The aim should be to explain as much as possible of the variance observed in all the parameters analysed. In order to result in a good explanation of variance the system of grouping should be as detailed as possible; however,

the units obtained should contain enough points to allow a proper application of statistical methods. Good explanations have been obtained by grouping according to soil typology and according to the substrate of soil formation (BUNDESANSTALT FÜR BODENWIRTSCHAFT, 1994).

THE SYSTEM OF TYPOLOGICAL UNITS:

Applying the above mentioned principles of grouping we arrived at a system of 29 typological units. The system is presented in Table 1.

The basis of these typological units is made up by the Austrian System of Soil Systematics and Soil Nomenclature (FINK, 1969). This publication represents the basis of all kinds of work in soil systematics in Austria. Because of the long time elapsed since 1969 and because of the rapid development of soil science during this time, the system is no longer totally satisfactory and is, therefore, now under discussion; this discussion, however, is not yet completed and thus the system is still in use.

For convenience of the symposium, where this paper was presented, the paper is presented in English language. To translate the original German terms into English it seemed advisable to use the terms of the FAO-nomenclature (FAO/UNESCO, 1990). It must be stressed, however, that this does not imply the application of FAO-definitions in the pedological classifications of the single sites. For clarification, the original German terms are also included in Table 1.

The figures in Table 1 show the Calcic Chernozems to be the most frequent soil in Lower Austria; they occupy some 20% of the agricultural area. They are followed by the Dystric Cambisols (on rock), having also nearly 20% of area.

Table 1:

Typological Units

Num.	Typological Unit	Frequency	%	percent cumulated
1	Calcaric Fluvisols kalkhaltige graue Auböden	22	1,5	1,5
2	Eutric Fluvisols vergleyte, kalkhaltige Graue Auböden	4	0,3	1,8
3	Eutric Fluvisols (brown) Braune Auböden, kalkhaltig (kalkfrei)	17	1,2	3,0
4	Eutric Fluvisols (brown, gleyic) vergleyte Braune Auböden, kalkhaltig und kalkfrei	7	0,5	3,5
5	Calcic Gleysols kalkhaltige Gleye	17	1,2	4,6
6	Dystric Gleysols kalkfreie Gleye	47	3,2	7,9
7	Rendzic Leptosols Rendsinen, Pararendsinen	32	2,2	10,1
8	Umbric Leptosols Ranker	11	0,8	10,8
9	Calcic Chernozems Tschernoseme, Braune Tschernoseme	299	20,6	31,5
10	Haplic Chernozems Paratschernoseme	22	1,5	33,0
11	Gleyic Chernozems Feuchtschwarzerden, meist kalkhaltig (vergleyt)	76	5,2	38,2
12	Calcaric Cambisols (on rock) kalkhaltige Felsbraunerden	40	2,8	41,0
13	Dystric Cambisols (on rock) kalkfreie Felsbraunerden	288	19,9	60,9
14	Calcaric Cambisols (on rock, gleyic) vergleyte, kalkhaltige Felsbraunerden	6	0,4	61,3
15	Dystric Cambisols (on rock, gleyic) vergleyte, kalkfreie Felsbraunerden	32	2,2	63,5
16	Calcaric Cambisols (on sediment) kalkhaltige Lockersediment-Braunerden	98	6,8	70,3

17	Dystric Cambisols (on sediment, gleyic) kalkfreie Lockersediment- Braunerden	41	2,8	73,1
18	Calcaric Cambisols (on sediment, gleyic) vergleyte, kalkhaltige Lockersediment-Braunerden	15	1,0	74,1
19	Dystric Cambisols (on sediment, gleyic) vergleyte, kalkfreie Lockersediment-Braunerden	45	3,1	77,2
20	Luvisols Parabraunerden, vereinzelt vergleyt	13	0,9	78,1
21	Planosols Pseudogleye	99	6,8	85,0
22	Ferralsols Braunlehme, Reliktböden	30	2,1	87,0
23	Planosols (relic) Relikt-pseudogleye	40	2,8	89,8
24	"Deposited Soils" (calcareous) kalkhaltige Kolluvien	47	3,2	93,0
25	"Deposited Soils" (calcareous, gleyic) vergleyte kalkhaltige Kolluvien	11	0,8	93,8
26	Anthrosols Kulturrohböden, Rigolböden	68	4,7	98,5
27	"Terric Histosols" Anmoore	9	0,6	99,1
28	Urbic Anthrosols Planieböden	5	0,3	99,4
29	Untypical Soils Untypische Böden	8	0,6	100,0

THE SYSTEM OF SUBSTRATUM UNITS:

The system of substratum units is presented in Table 2. Also, the original German terms are included in the table. By chance, there are also 29 substratum units. The most frequent substratum of soil formation in Lower Austria is less, followed by older, calcareous alluvial sediments and by granites of the Bohemian massif.

Table 2:

Substratum - Units

Num.	Substratum - Unit	Frequency	%	% cumul.
1	Planished Material Planiematerial	2,0	0,1	0,1
2	Cumulic Material, calcareous Krumen - u. Kolluvialmat. , kalkhaltig	52,0	3,6	3,7
3	Cumulic Material, non - calcareous Krumen - u. Kolluvialmat. , kalkfrei	8,0	0,6	4,3
4	Alluvial Sediments, calcareous Schwemmateriale, kalkhaltig	103,0	7,1	11,4
5	Alluvial Sediments, non - calc. Schwemmateriale, kalkfrei	37,0	2,6	13,9
6	Older Alluvial Sediments, calc. älteres Schwemmateriale, kalkhaltig	149,0	10,3	24,2
7	Older Alluvial Sediments, non - calcareous älteres Schwemmateriale, kalkfrei	19,0	1,3	25,5
8	Relic Soil Material reliktes Bodenmateriale	10,0	0,7	26,2
9	Old Silicate Weathered Material altes kristallines Verwitterungsmateriale	44,0	3,0	29,3
10	Quaternary Sediments, calc. Quartärsediment, kalkhaltig	48,0	3,3	32,6
11	Quaternary Sediments, non - calc. Quartärsediment, kalkfrei	23,0	1,6	34,2
12	Loess Löß	272,0	18,8	52,9
13	Pleistocene Loam Decklehm	58,0	4,0	56,9
14	Molasse, calcareous Molasse, kalkhaltig	48,0	3,3	60,2
15	Molasse, non - calcareous Molasse, kalkfrei	31,0	2,1	62,4

16	Waschberg - Zone Waschbergzone	9,0	0,6	63,0
17	Tertiary Sediments, calcareous Tertiärsediment, kalkhaltig	40,0	2,8	65,8
18	Tertiary Sediments, non - calcareous Tertiärsediment, kalkfrei	18,0	1,2	67,0
19	Flysch, calcareous Flysch, kalkhaltig	14,0	1,0	68,0
20	Flysch, non - calcareous Flysch, kalkfrei	81,0	5,6	73,6
21	Northern Limestone Alps, calca - reous Material Nördliche Kalkalpen, kalkhaltig	52,0	3,6	77,2
22	Northern Limestone Alps, non - calcareous Material Nördliche Kalkalpen, kalkfrei	26,0	1,8	79,0
23	Grauwacken - Zone Grauwackenzone	4,0	0,3	79,2
24	Central - Alpine Material Zentralalpin (Semmering, Wechsel)	55,0	3,8	83,0
25	Bohemian Massif - Granulite Böhm. Masse, Granulit	7,0	0,5	83,5
26	Bohemian Massif - Rastenberger Granodiorit Böhm. Masse, Rastenberger Granodiorit	8,0	0,6	84,1
27	Bohemian Massif - Schist, Gneiss, Marble Böhm. Masse, Schiefer, Gneis, Marmor	104,0	7,2	91,2
28	Bohemian Massif - Granite Böhm. Masse, Granit	113,0	7,8	99,0
29	Bohemian Massif - Ultrabasite Böhm. Masse, Ultrabasit	14,0	1,0	100,0

THE COMBINATION OF TYPOLOGICAL AND SUBSTRATUM UNITS:

Both, typological and substratum units were a successful basis of grouping, able to explain a large part of the variance observed (BUNDESANSTALT FÜR BODENWIRTSCHAFT; 1994). Thus, a combination of the two principals seemed

advisable, resulting in units of the kind "soil type on soil forming substratum". Table 3 shows the 29 x 29 theoretical possibilities of combination. The table lists the number of points for the respective combination. It can be seen that many of the cells are without any point; that means, the combination does not exist, either not at all or not in Lower Austria. (Table 3)

The table further shows quite a large number of cells comprising only two principles does not result in a practicable system of grouping.

In cases with larger numbers of points, however, the combination is well practicable for example, the table presents a useful subdivision of the Calcic Chernozems, which can be seen to occur on a number of different substrata. Statistical analyses, which will be published elsewhere, show significant differences in the properties of Chernozems on different substrata.

To succeed in a final system of soil units of the kind mentioned above we decided to use a hierarchy: One of the two systems of grouping should form the first level of hierarchy and should be applied in every case. The other system should form the second level and should be applied only if the number of points allows a further subdivision of the unit.

FINAL SOIL UNITS, FREQUENCY AND AREAL DISTRIBUTION:

Using this hierarchy we arrived at a final system of soil units in the agricultural area of Lower Austria. We decided to use the typological system as the first level and the substratum system as the second level of hierarchy the application of the typological system will result in units, that of the substratum system in sub - units. The final soil units and sub - units as well as their frequency are presented in Table 4. The table is arranged in a decreasing order of areas occupied by the soil units. The areal distribution of units and sub - units is presented in maps Ns 2 to 30 in the appendix of this paper. Properties of these soil units and statistical differences as well as at the level of units as at that of sub - units will be published elsewhere.

Table 4:

Frequencies of Units

Num.	Calcic Chernozems (9)	299	n	%
1	on Loess (12)		154	10,6
2	on Older Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (6)		75	5,2
3	on Quarternary Sediments, calcareous (10)		24	1,7
4	on Tertiary Sediments, calcareous (17)		16	1,1
5	on Molasse, calcareous (14)		12	0,8
6	on Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (4)		11	0,8
7	on other Substrates (2,16)		7	0,5

Num.	Dystric Cambisols (on rock) (13)	288	n	%
8	on Bohemian Massif - Granite (28)		100	6,9
9	on Boh. Mass. - Schist, Gneiss, Marble (27)		81	5,6
10	on Central Alpine Material (24)		50	3,5
11	on Flysch, non - calcareous (20)		20	1,4
12	on Bohemian Massif - Ultrabasite (29)		12	0,8
13	on other Substrates (18,21,22,23,25,26)		25	1,7

Num.	Planosols (21)	99	n	%
14	on Pleistocene Loam (13)		33	2,3
15	on Flysch, non - calcareous (20)		32	2,2
16	on Molasse, non - calcareous (15)		11	0,8
17	on other Substrates (5,7,8,10,11,12,14,18,19,21,22,29)		23	1,6

Num.	Calcaric Cambisols (on sediments) (16)	98	n	%
18	on Loess (12)		46	3,2
19	on Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (4)		16	1,1
20	on Molasse, calcareous (14)		15	1,0
21	on other Substrates (2,6,10,16,17,21)		21	1,4

Num.	Gleyic Chernozems (11)	76	n	%
22	on Older Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (6)		49	3,4
23	on other Substrates (2,4,5,7,10,14,17)		27	1,9

Num.	Anthrosols (26)	68	n	%
24	on Loess (12)		48	3,3
25	on other Substrates (2,6,10,14,15,16,17,27)		20	1,4

Num.	Dystric Gleysols (6)	47	n	%
26	on Alluvial Sediments, non - calcareous (5)		16	1,1
27	on Bohemian Massif - Granite (28)		10	0,7
28	on other Substrates (2,3,9,18,20,22,27)		21	1,4

Num.	"Deposited Soils" (calcareous) (24)	47	n	%
29	on Cumulic Material, calcareous (2)		30	2,1
30	on other Substrates (4,6,10,12,14,16)		17	1,2

Num.	Dystric Cambisols (on sediment, gleyic) (19)	45	n	%
31	on Pleistocene Loam (13)		17	1,2
32	on Molasse, non - calcareous (15)		13	0,9
33	on other Substrates (3,5,9,11,18,20,22,27)		15	1,0

Num.	Dystric Cambisols (on sediment) (17)	41	n	%
34	on different Substrates (3,5,7,8,11,13,15,18,20,22,24,27)		41	2,8

Num.	Calcaric Cambisols (on rock) (12)	40	n	%
35	on Northern Limestone Alps, calc. Mat. (21)		24	1,7
36	on other Substrates (14,17,19,24,27,28)		16	1,1

Num.	Planosols (relic) (23)	40	n	%
37	on Old Silicate Weathered Material (9)		39	2,7
38	on Bohemian Massif - Granulite (25)		1	0,1

Num.	Rendzic Leptosols (7)	32	n	%
39	on Older Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (6)		12	0,8
40	on Northern Limestone Alps, calc. Mat.(21)		9	0,6
41	on other Substrates (4,10,14,16,17)		11	0,8

Num.	Dystric Cambisols (on rock, gleyic) (15)	32	n	%
42	on Flysch, non - calcareous (20)		15	1,0
43	on other Substrates (22,24,25,27,29)		17	1,2

Num.	Ferralsols (22)	30	n	%
44	on Northern Limestone Alps, calc. Mat. (21)		14	1,0
45	on other Substrates (8,12,18,20,22)		16	1,1

Num.	Calcaric Fluvisols (1)	22	n	%
46	on Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (4)		22	1,5

Num.	Haplic Chernozems (10)	22	n	%
47	on Older Alluvial Sediments, non - calc. (7)		10	0,7
48	on Quarternary Sediments, non - calc. (11)		10	0,7
49	on other Substrates (5,18)		2	0,1

Num.	Eutric Fluvisols (brown) (3)	17	n	%
50	on Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (4)		13	0,9
51	on other Substrates (5,10)		4	0,3

Num.	Calcic Gleysols (5)	17	n	%
52	on Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (4)		12	0,8
53	on other Substrates (2,6,12)		5	0,3

Num.	Calcaric Cambisols (on sed. , gleyic) (18)	15	n	%
54	on different Substrates (4,10,12,14,17)		15	1,0

Num.	Luviosols (20)	13	n	%
55	on different Substrates (10,11,12,13,18)		13	0,9

Num.	Umbric Leptosols (8)	11	n	%
56	on different Substrates (20,22,24,27,28)		11	0,8

Num.	“Deposited Soils” (calc. , gleyic) (25)	11	n	%
57	on different Substrates (2,12)		11	0,8

Num.	“Terric Histosols” (27)	9	n	%
58	on different Substrates (4,5,6)		9	0,6

Num.	Untypical Soils (29)	8	n	%
59	on different Substrates (7,8,9,15,19,27)		8	0,6

Num.	Eutric Fluvisols (brown, gleyic) (4)	7	n	%
60	on different Substrates (4,5)		7	0,5

Num.	Calcaric Cambisols (on rock, gleyic) (14)	6	n	%
61	on different Substrates (14,19,21)		6	0,4

Num.	Urbic Anthrosols (28)	5	n	%
62	on different Substrates (1,10,15,19)		5	0,3

Num.	Eutric Fluvisols (2)	4	n	%
63	on Alluvial Sediments, calcareous (4)		4	0,3

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Namen und Anschrift der Autoren:

Otto DANNEBERG

Bundesanstalt für Bodenwirtschaft

Denisgasse 31 - 33

A - 1200 Wien

Austria

Ilse POVOLNY

Bundesanstalt für Bodenwirtschaft

Denisgasse 31 - 33

A - 1200 Wien

Austria

Helga GOTTSCHLING

Forstliche Bundesversuchsanstalt

Seckendorff-Gutend-Weg 8

Tirolergarten

A - 1131 Wien

Austria

Othmar NESTROY

Institut für Technische Geologie und Angewandte Mineralogie

Technische Universität Graz

Rechbauerstr. 12

A - 8010 Graz

Austria

Appendix: Maps Ns 1 - 30. (M. WANDL, BZI MAP).

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 1
NETWORK OF
SAMPLING POINTS

Legende:

- Basic Point, Arable Land
 - ▣ Basic Point, Grass Land
 - ▨ Add. Point, Arable Land
 - ▧ Add. Point, Grass Land
- M=1:1069000

BZIMAP: M. Wandi, BAW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 2
CALCIC CHERNOZEMS

Legende:

- on Loess
- on Old. Alluv. Sed., calc.
- on Quaternary Sed., calc.
- on Tertiary Sed., calc.
- on Molasse, calcareous
- on Alluv. Sed., calc.
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1069000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 9
"DEPOSITED SOILS"
(calcareous)

Legende:

on Cumulic Material, calc

on other Substrates

other Units

M=1:1069000

EZMAP: M. Wandl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 4
PLANOSOLS

Legende:

- on Plistocene loam
 - on Fyisch, non-calcareous
 - on Molasse, non-calcareous
 - on other Substrates
 - other Units
- M=1:1069000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 5
CALCARIC CAMBISOLS
(on Sediments)

Legende:

- on Loess
- on Alluv. Sed., calc.
- on Molasse, calcareous
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 6
GLEYIC CHERNOSEMS

Legende:

- on Old. Alluv. Sed, calc
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map N. 7
ANTHROSOLS

Legende:

- on Loess
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 8
DYSTRIC GLEYSOLS

Legende:

- on Alluv. Sed. non-calc.
- on Bohem. Massif-Granite
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wandl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 9
"DEPOSITED SOILS"
(calcareous)

Legende:

- on Cumulic Material, calc
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BUBW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 10
DYSTRIC CAMBISOLS
(on Sediments, gleyic)

Legende:

- on Pleistocene loam
 - on Molasse, non-calc.
 - on other Substrates
 - other Units
- M=1:1069000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 11
DYSTRIC CAMBISOLS
(on Sediment)

Legende:

- on different Substrates
 - other units
- M=1:1069000

BZIMAP: M. Wondl, BASW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Mod Nr. 12
CALCARIC CAMBISOLS
(on Rock)

Legende

- on North. Limestone Alps, calc. Mt.
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1000000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 13
PLANOSOLS
(relic)

Legende:

- on Old Silicate Weathered Mor
- on Bohemian Massif-Granulite
- other Units

M=1:1089000

BZMAP: M. Wendl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 14
RENDZIC LEPTOSOLS

Legende:

- on Older Alluvial Sediments, calc.
 - on North. Limestone Alps, calc. Mol
 - on other Substrates
 - other Units
- M=1:100000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map N. 15
DYSTRIC CAMBISOLS
(on Rock, gleyic)

Legende:

- on Flysch, non-calcareous
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wandi, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 16
FERRALSOLS

Legende:

on North Limestone Alps calc. Marl

on other Substrates

other Units

M=1:100000

BZMAP- M. Wondt, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 17
CALCARIC FLUVISOILS

Legende:

on Alluvial Sediments, calc.

other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 18
HAPLIC CHERNOZEMS

Legende:

- on Older Alluv. Sediments, non-calcs
 - on Quaternary Sediments, non-calcs
 - on other Substrates
 - other Units
- #=1:100000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 19
EUTRIC FLUVISOLS
(brown)

Legende:

- on Alluvial Sediments, calc
- on other Substrates
- other Units

M=1:1069000

BZLWAP: M. Wondl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 20
CALCIC GLEYSOLS

Legende:

on Alluvial Sediments, calc

on other Substrates

other Units

M=1:1069000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 21
CALCARIC CAMBISOLS
(on Sed., gleyic)

Legende:

■ on different Substrates

□ other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BAGW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 22
LUMSOLS

Legende:

■ on different Substrates

□ other Units

M=1:1069000

BEZMAP: M. Wandl, BABW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft
Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 23
UMBRIC LEPTOSOLS

Legende:

- on different Substrates
 - other Units
- M=1:1069000

BZIMAP- M. Wondl, BAW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 24
"DEPOSITED SOILS"
(calc., gleyic)

Legende:

on different Substrates

other Units

M=1:1069000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 25
"TERRIC HISTOSOLS"

Legende:

on different Substrates

other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BAW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 26
UNYTYPICAL SOILS

Legende:

on different Substrates

other Units

M=1:1069000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 27
EUTRIC FLUVISOLS
(brown, gleyic)

Legende:

- on different Substrates
 - other Units
- M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BRGW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 28
CALCARIC CAMBISOLS
(on Rock, gleyic)

Legende:

■ on different Substrates

□ other Units

M=1:1069000

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 29
URBIC ANTHROSOLS

Legende:

on different Substrates

other Units

M=1:1069000

821MAP: M. Wendi, BBSW

Bundesanstalt f.
Bodenwirtschaft

Soil Units in
Lower Austria

Map Nr. 30
EUTRIC FLUVISOLS

Legende:

■ on Alluvial Sediments, calc

□ other Units

M=1:1069000

BZMAP: M. Wondl, BABW

PEDO-ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE LAND EVALUATION AND LAND USE PLANNING

M. DŽATKO, J. VILČEK

Among final targets of the basic soil properties research is the purposeful interpretation for practical topics solution, namely for the rational land use option. This is particularly significant, specially there, where is occurring disharmony among soil properties and environment, and man requirements, namely where these problem solution is conditioned by market.

Therefore landscape conversation and healthy food security inspired and has been inspiring pedologists to elaborate such soil use system that would be guarantee of the required harmony among soil productivity potential, agricultural landscape stability and sufficient amount of sound foods.

As the soil is an organic part of ecosystem, projected systems of the land use option cannot be based only on the partial soil properties knowledge (e. g. generic, physical properties, available soil nutrient contents), but on detailed relationship analysis, as large environment factors number as possible, including economical analysis. Therefore we are coming out of detailed data on characteristics and structure already integrated pedo-ecological units in scale 1 : 5000, and from attained their productivity potential assessment systems, including factor analysis, as well as energetical and economical efficiency of crops grown evaluation.

These analysis results are unambiguously confirming, the energetical and economical efficiencies of plant production are primarily conditioned by characteristics of soil and environment, i. e. proper site selection and crop rotation. Every overlapping the natural boundaries of the concrete crop and cul-

ture grown suitability has not only economical, but also ecological impacts. Real starting point background is the system of typological-production categories (Džatko, M. et al., 1981, 1985, 1993), by means of them is determined not only type of use (field, meadow, forest), but also productivity presumption of given territory in detailed map 1 : 5000. This category implementation modifies also relationship between territory potential and man requirements, particularly in marginal territories. Proper crop and culture allocation is one of the most effective means for antierosion conservation. This procedure has not only ecological, but also positives, as it a priori is excluding any possibility of unproper production allocation.

The proposed land use option system could be possibly used not only for macro- or mezoconcept solution in the level of national policy, but also in the level of concrete farms.

Eines der Ziele der Erfassung von Basisdaten der Böden ist eine optimale Landnutzung. Dies ist dort von besonderer Wichtigkeit, wo eine Disharmonie zwischen den Bodeneigenschaften, der Umwelt und den Bedürfnissen des Menschen (meist vom Markt gesteuert), besteht.

Deshalb kann seitens der Landschaftserhalter und Ernährungswissenschaftler an die Bodenkundler die Anregung, ein solches Bodennutzungssystem zu erarbeiten, das Garant für die gewünschte Harmonie zwischen dem Bodenproduktivitätspotential, der Landschaftsstabilität und der ausreichenden Produktion gesunder Nahrungsmittel sein soll.

Da der Boden den organischen Teil des Ökosystems darstellt, dürfen die Kriterien für eine optimale Landnutzung nicht nur auf der Kenntnis der Bodeneigenschaften, z. B. den genetischen, chemischen und physikalischen, basieren, sondern auch auf einer detaillierten Analyse verwandter Formen. Deshalb wird von den Daten und der Struktur der pedo-ökologischen Einheiten im Maßstab 1:5.000 und von den steuerlich erfaßten Produktionspotential ausgegangen, wobei auch die Ergebnisse der Faktoranalyse und des energetischen wie ökonomischen Ertragszuwachses Berücksichtigung finden.

Die Resultate bestätigen eindeutig, daß die energetische und ökonomische Pflanzenproduktion primär von den Bodencharakteristika und der Umgebung abhängig sind, d.h. speziell von der Lage und dem Fruchtwechsel. Jede Überschreitung naturgegebener Grenzen im Anbau bestimmter Pflanzen bringt nicht nur ökonomische, sondern auch ökologische Schäden. Günstige Bedingungen bestehen in der Anwendung des Systems der typologischen Produktivitätskategorien (Džatko, M., u.a., 1981, 1985, 1993), mit dessen Hilfe nicht nur die richtige Nutzungsart (Feld, Wiese, Wald), sondern auch die Produktivitätsvoraussetzung eines betreffenden Territoriums auf einer Karte im Maßstab 1:5.000 ermittelt werden können. Diese Vorgangsweise gestattet auch ein Abwägen zwischen Territoriumspotential und Bedürfnissen des Menschen, insbesondere in den Grenzterritorien.

Eine geeignete Fruchtfolge ist nach wie vor die beste Methode gegen Bodenerosion und damit für die Bodenerhaltung. Diese ökologischen Positiva lassen keine Wahl für eine standortswidrige Fruchtfolge zu.

Dieses vorgeschlagene Landnutzungssystem könnte nicht nur im Makro- und Mesobereich der Landwirtschaft, sondern auch konkret von landwirtschaftlichen Großbetrieben angewandt werden.

Medzi cieľovým výskumom bazických pôdných vlastností je účelová interpretácia pre užívanie pôdy. Toto je dôležité obzvlášť tam, kde je disharmónia medzi pôdnymi vlastnosťami, životným prostredím a potrebami človeka, menovite tam, kde je toto problémové riešenie podmienené trhom.

Preto inšpirovala ochrana pôdy a zdravých potravín pedológov vypracovať taký systém pre využívanie pôdy, aby bol garantom želanej harmónie medzi produktivitou pôdy, stabilitou krajiny a dostatočným množstvom zdravých potravín.

Keďže pôda je organická časť ekosystému, nesmú projektované systémy využívania pôdy vychádzať len z čiastkových poznatkov pôdy (napr. obrábania, fyzikálne vlastnosti, potravinové jednotky), ale aj z detailnej príbuzenskej analýzy. Preto vychádzame z detailnej datovej charakteristiky štruktúr v integrovaných pedo-ekologických jednotkách v mierke 1:5000 a z do-

siahnutých radiaciach schopností produkčného potenciálu , spolu s faktorovou analýzou ako aj z energetickej a ekologickej efektivity porastov. Výsledky analýzy potvrdzujú jednoznačne, že energetický a ekonomický užitočný výkon rastlinnej produkcie je primárne závislý od pôdnej charakteristiky a okolia, to znamená obzvlášť výber polohy a obmieňanie plodov. Každé prekrytie prirodzených hraníc vhodnosti výsadby konkrétnych rastlín má nielen ekonomické ale aj ekologické dôsledky (zlé následky). Reálnym počiatkom skupina je systém typologických produkčných kategórií (Džatko, M., a kol. 1981, 1985, 1993), pomocou ktorej je udaná nielen typologické použitie (pole, lúka, les), ale aj produkčná schopnosť dotýčajúcej oblasti na detailnej mape v mierke 1:5000. Toto prevedenie kategórií modifikuje a súvislosti medzi územným potenciálom a potrebami človeka, obzvlášť v hraničných oblastiach. Vhodná voľba rozloženia plodín patrí k najefektívnejším prostriedkom antieróznej ochrany. Tento spôsob má nielen ekologické pozitíva, ale zároveň vylučuje a priori nevhodné rozloženie produktov. Navrhovaný systém výberu využiteľnosti pôdy môže byť využitý nielen pre makro- a mezokonceptné riešenie na úrovni národného hospodárstva, ale aj na úrovni konkrétnych fariem.

Name und Anschrift der Verfasser:

Michal DŽATKO; Jozef VILČEK
Soil Fertility Research Institute
Gagarinova 10
827 13 Bratislava
Slovak Republic

ASSESSMENT OF SOIL WATER REGIME

E. FULAJTÁR

SUMMARY

The article gives the characterization of the alluvial soils with deep, high and middle deep ground water table on the principles of the zoning and ecological classification of the soil water regime. The spatial and temporal variability of the soil water is evaluated. It may serve as a model for interpreting and understanding the soil water and soil moisture regime.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Zonen des Bodenwassers und der ökologische Klassifikation des Wasserregimes sind durch tiefen, hohen und mittleren Wasserspiegel des Grundwassers charakterisiert. Dieser Beitrag befaßt sich mit der Klassifikation der Raum- Zeit Variabilität der Bodenfeuchte. Diese Daten können als Modell für die Interpretation von Wasser- Feuchtigkeitsregimen und auch für praktische Anwendungen dienen.

SÚHRN

Na princípoch vymedzenia zón pôdnej vody a ekologickej klasifikácie vodného režimu pôdy sú charakterizované aluviálne pôdy s hlbokou, vysokou a stredne hlbokou hladinou podzemnej vody. Príspevok hodnotí priestorovú a časovú variabilitu obsahu pôdnej vody. Môže slúžiť ako model pre interpretáciu a praktické využívanie údajov o vodnom a vlhkosťnom režime pôd.

INTRODUCTION

In accordance with Rode's definition (1963) under the conception of soil water regime we understand all phenomena of increase, distribution, retention and disbursement of the soil water in the soil root zone during the given time period. Under the root zone we understand soil and substrate layer which influences plants by water supply. This layer is called soil-rock layer in terrestrial soils or pedohydrological profile in alluvial soils.

A given time period during which the soil water regime is evaluated is regularly one or more successive hydrological years. As a hydrological year the period since October to September of the next year is understood.

Fundamental element of the soil water regime is the soil moisture regime which represents all increases and decreases of moisture content in certain soil layer during a time period.

From quantitative and qualitative point of view the soil water and soil moisture regime can be pressed by :

- zoning of the soil water regime
- ecological classification of the soil moisture

According to the definition, all the water held in soil between the soil surface and the ground water levels is soil water. Since not all the soil water is influenced by the root activity Kristensen (1975) divided the soil water into 5 main zones (Figure 1). Starting from the soil surface towards the ground water table Kristensen (1975) characterized as the zones as follows.

The evaporation zone is the layer of soil profile between the soil surface and so called the thermocline level. The evaporation zone which lies above the thermocline is a transition or barrier zone between the atmosphere and the soil proper. It is generally rather thin layer and it may consist of more or less loosened mineral or organic soil, plant residue, different kinds of mulching material or their mixture.

The transpiration zone is the layer of soil between the thermocline level and the maximum root depth level. The maximum root depth is the maximum

Figure 1

Profile zoning of soil water regime

depth from which plants extract water. The drying out in this zone is caused mainly by the plant transpiration.

The evaporation and transpiration zones constitute together the **root zone**. **The intermediate zone** is the layer of soil between the maximum root depth level and the capillary level. The capillary level is the maximum height above the water table to which water can rise by capillary action.

In the territories where the ground water by capillary rise reaches the transpiration zone, the intermediate zone does not occur.

The water content in this zone varies only due to the water vapour diffusion to the root zone in dry periods or due to the infiltration during periods with the surplus precipitation.

In territories with low humidity the layers with higher and low water content are in the intermediate zone. These layers Fulajtár (1989) indicated as adding subzone and subzone with low store of soil water.

Adding subzone is characterized with rather high and relatively constant content of the capillary hanged up soil water.

The subzone with low store of soil water is characterized by the low and constant water content. It occurs in the soils with deep ground water level.

The capillary zone is the layer of soil between the capillary level and the saturation level. The saturation level is the height above the groundwater level to which all the pores are filled by capillary action.

Four above mentioned zones make up together the **aeration or unsaturated zone**, characterized by a fraction of aerated pores.

The capillary fringe zone is the layer of soil between the saturation level and the groundwater level.

The capillary fringe zone together with the four previously mentioned zones makes up the **soil water zone**.

The qualitative assessment of the soil water regime is based on the energetic conditions. The recommended classification, given in the table 1, was suggested by Kutílek (1968,1978). In this classification the whole range of soil moisture is divided into 6 moisture intervals. Boundaries between the moisture intervals are main hydrolimits: Saturation (S), Field (retention) capacity, FC (RC), Point of decreased availability (PDA), Wilting point (WP) and Hygroscopic coefficient (HC).

Table 1

CLASSIFICATION OF SOIL MOISTURE

NOISTURE INTERVAL	SYMBOL	MOISTURE RANGE	pF
Aquatic state	Θ_S	Full saturation to saturation	below 1,2
Uvidic interval	$\Theta_S - \Theta_{RC}$	Saturation to retention (field) capacity	1,2 - 3,2
Semiuvidic interval	$\Theta_{RC} - \Theta_{PDA}$	Retention capacity to point of decreased availability	2,2 - 3,2
Semiarid interval	$\Theta_{PDA} - \Theta_{WP}$	Point of decreased availability to wilting point	3,2 - 4,2
Arid interval	$\Theta_{WP} - \Theta_{HC}$	Wilting point to hygroscopic coefficient	4,2 - 5,2
Hyperarid interval	$< \Theta_{HC}$	below hygroscopic coefficient	above 5,2

Practical use of this classification worked out.

The moisture intervals may be characterized as follows. **The aquatic state** implies that all pores are filled with water. The volumetric water content is equal the porosity.

The uvidic interval implies that all the capillary and part of the non capillary pores are filled with water. The soil is overmoist and usually weakly aerated, especially in the compacted soils.

The semiuvidic interval is most favourable. It creates good supply of available water and sufficient air to the plant growth.

The semiarid interval characterizes such a state of the soil moisture when the soil water is no longer in the movement. Therefore only that section is available to plants which is in the close contact with the plant roots.

The arid interval is characterized by the insufficiency of available water and by the great soil aeration.

The hyperarid interval. The moisture content is lower than the hygroscopic coefficient. This interval is very rare. It can be supposed in thin surface soil layer which is in the direct contact with atmosphere.

2 RESULTS

2.1 Zoning of soil water regime

The profile zones defined in preface are generally difficult to delineate precisely under the field conditions. How it looks in the natural conditions is shown on the figures no. 2-4.

The zoning of the soil water regime in soil with the deep ground water table shows figure 2.

Pedohydrological profile is above 6 m deep, the ground water table fluctuates roughly from 5,5 to 6,5 m, during the higher waterflow periods it rises higher.

The soil moisture content is expressed by the moisture isolines in 5 volumetric percentage intervals.

The transpiration zone, intermediate zone divided into adding and low store soil water subzones and capillary zone are seen on the figure .

The transpiration zone is approximately deep 1,7 m. It is characterized by the distinct soil moisture dynamics caused by the evapotranspiration or infiltration of the precipitation.

The intermediate adding subzone is running from 1,7 to 3,5 m. It contains rather high (30-40%) and more-less constant water content.

The intermediate low store water subzone is running from 3-5 m to capillary zone. It is characterized by the low moisture content during the whole pursued period (10-15 %).

The capillary zone is distinct above the groundwater table and its thickness varies from 10 to 70 cm. In the case of the high ground water table rise the capillary zone is connected with the intermediate zone.

The zoning of the soil water regime in soil with the high ground water table, which fluctuates in the depth approximately 1,5 m shows figure 3.

On this figure we can identify the transpiration and capillary zones.

The transpiration zone is rather shallow. It is 0.8 m deep only. The drying of this zone caused by the evapora transpiration is weak, because of the capillary action.

The capillary zone is connected with the transpiration zone and from 0,8 m down to the ground water table contains 35-40% of soil water.

The zoning of the soil water regime in soil with middle ground water table depth shows figure 4.

Pedohydrological profile is deep only 2,5 m, ground water table fluctuates from 2 to 2,5 m.

In this case the transpiration zone reaches to the depth of 2 m. Capillary zone is less marked.

2.2 Assessment of soil moisture regime

Practical use of the ecological soil moisture classification shows figure 5 where the water content and main hydrolimits are expressed in mm of the water column per 1 m thick soil layer.

SOIL WATER ZONES IN SOIL WITH HIGH GROUND WATER TABLE

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

From the figure it can be concluded that soil moisture regime observed in characterized soil is very favourable from both the plants demands and the pedogenesis.

The water content is predominantly running in the most favourable - semiuvitic interval. Only in some summer months it drops up to the semiarid interval. The plants have sufficiency of the available water and air. Water - air and oxidation - reduction conditions in the soil profile are optimal.

3 CONCLUSION

The zoning and ecological classification of the soil water regime that has been presented are important as a model for interpreting and understanding the spacial and temporal variability of soil water and its availability for plant growth.

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Name und Anschrift des Verfassers:

Emil FULAJTÁR

Soil Fertility Research Institute

Gagarinova 10

827 13 Bratislava

Slovak Republic

SOIL MONITORING ON THE TERRITORY INFLUENCED BY CONSTRUCTION OF THE HYDRO-SYSTEM GABČÍKOVO

E.FULAJTÁR

SUMMARY

The purpose of soil monitoring is, based on a long-term assessment of selected group of soil properties, to evaluate the changes and development trends of soil properties in relation to the their reference state and in relation to the altered groundwater levels evoked by construction of the hydro-system Gabčíkovo.

The article summarizes the results of soils moisture and groundwater table monitoring obtained in 1990-1992, i.e. before the hydro-system Gabčíkovo started to operate and in 1993, i.e. after it.

The obtained results shows, that the prognosed negative changes of the groundwater levels did not appear and soil moisture regime is preserved in the original state. All other soil properties should be therefore preserved without changes.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Ab dem Jahre 1989 werden die Auswirkungen des Kraftwerks Gabčíkovo auf die Böden und deren Eigenschaften kontrolliert. Es werden folgende Eigenschaften kontrolliert:

- Bodenfeuchtigkeit im gesamten Profil (in Dekaden) in Abhängigkeit mit der Wasserhöhe;

- monatlich, während der Vegetationsperiode, die biologische Aktivität;
- ein Mal pro Jahr die Menge und die Art von Humus und Salzbildung;
- zwei Mal pro Jahr, Frühling (April) und Herbst (September), der Chemismus des Grundwassers;
- chemische und physikalische Grunddaten, erstmalig vor Errichtung des Kraftwerks, dann in einem 5jährigen Zyklus.

Die Daten, die durch die laufende Beobachtung in den Jahren 1989 bis 1992 gewonnen werden konnten, zeigen den Stand vor der Inbetriebnahme und sind somit die Bezugsdaten für alle folgenden Auswertungen.

Erste Resultate von Messungen nach der Inbetriebnahme lassen nur kleine Veränderungen im Grundwasserbereich der Böden erkennen, dadurch haben einstweilen das Bodenwasserregime und andere Bodeneigenschaften keine Änderung erfahren.

SÚHRN

Cieľom monitoringu pôd je na základe dlhodobého sledovania vybraného súboru pôdnych vlastností hodnotiť ich zmeny a vývojové trendy vo vzťahu k ich referenčnému stavu a vo vzťahu k zmeneným hladinám podzemnej vody spôsobenými výstavbou VD Gabčíkovo.

Príspevok sumarizuje výsledky monitoringu vlhkosti pôd a hladín podzemných vôd, získané pred uvedením vodného diela do prevádzky (r. 1990-1992) a v prvom roku jeho činnosti (1993).

Získané výsledky ukazujú, že po uvedení vodného diela do prevádzky, prognozované negatívne zmeny hladín podzemnej vody nenastali a vlhkosťný režim pôd sa zachoval v pôvodnom stave. Zmeny ostatných pôdnych vlastností sa preto nepredpokladajú.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that hydro-power plants that were built on rivers in broad alluvial plains changed the groundwater table and through this change they influenced soil properties, mainly soil moisture regime and environmental conditions as a whole.

From this point of view in the territory Žitný ostrov, influenced by hydro-system Gabčíkovo, the following areas were assumed (Gažovič 1988):

- Area with the groundwater table rise
- Area with the groundwater table fall
- Area without groundwater table changes

Area with rising groundwater table (Figure 1) covers the upper part of Žitný ostrov. Original groundwater table, before the hydro-system Gabčíkovo started to operate was in the depth of 4-8 m, and after this operation it rose up to 3-2 m, below the surface. The groundwater rising was caused by water infiltration from the water reservoir into surroundings.

Area with groundwater table fall covers the middle part of Žitný ostrov. Groundwater table is in the depth 1-3 m. The groundwater fall down to 3-4 m was assumed as a consequence of the waterflow lowering in old Danube riverbed and impermeability of the inlet channel. Due to this negative prognosis the project of Gabčíkovo hydro-system was changed in such a way that more water was released to the old riverbed, and to the natural river branches and agricultural channel system, according to actual water demands of ecosystems. These changes of the project caused that groundwater level was not changed.

Area without groundwater table changes covers lower part of Žitný ostrov. The original groundwater table in the depth of 2-3 m is still preserved.

The real effect of the Gabčíkovo hydro-system on the soil properties is followed by soil monitoring (Fulajtár et al. 1991).

Data collection for soil monitoring was implemented on the net of the stationer monitoring sites. (Figure 1). Twenty monitoring agriculturally used plots

were chosen on the touched territory. Three sites (Mp 1-3) are located in the area with rising groundwater table, eleven (Mp 4-14) in te area with assumed lowering groundwater table and six (Mp15-20) in the area without groundwater table changes.

Each monitoring site consist of :

- pedological profile
- moisture probe
- hydrogeological borehole
- vessel for measurement of atmosferic precipitation and irrigation water

Pedological profile.

Pedological profile was described in detail to the depth of 1,2 m. From each diagnostic horizon samples were taken and analysed to characterize chemical and physical properties at so called starting point, i.e. before the hydro-system Gabčíkovo started to operate. Sampling for continuing monitoring is done by auguring using former morphological description of the soil profiles.

Moisture probe.

This is an iron tube coated by zinc installed to the soil. Its lower part is impermeably closed, upper part is equipped by lockable cover. The moisture probe serves for monitoring of soil moisture content by neutron method.

Hydrogeological borehole

Hydrogeological borehole serves for groundwater table monitoring and water sampling for determination of groundwater chemistry.

The following basic characteristics are measured and evaluated at each monitored site:

- soil moisture for each 10 cm layer until the groundwater table in decade intervals. Together with moisture content the height of groundwater table and precipitation are measured.

FIGURE 1

- biological properties of the soils ones per month during vegetation period
- humus content, its quality and processes of salinization and alkalization, ones per year
- basic physical, chemical and agrochemical properties, at the beginning of the monitoring and than in 5 year intervals
- chemical composition of the groundwater, twice a year, at spring (April) and at the end of summer (September)

Data obtained during the period 1989-1992 were evaluated as so called starting point or starting state which serves as a reference for comparison of the soil properties development after setting the Water Work into operation. Data obtained in 1993 characterized situation in first year after setting Water Work Gabčíkovo into working.

2. RESULTS

In this article are presented the results of the soil moisture and groundwater table regimes.

Both phenomena, the groundwater table and soil moisture dynamics are characterized on:

- figure 2 for area with rising of the groundwater table
- figure 3 for area with assumed fall of the groundwater table
- figure 4 for area without groundwater table changes

2.1. Area with rising of the groundwater table

This area is characterized by the results obtained on the monitoring plot Mp 2 (Figure 2) The groundwater table is predominantly in the 5-6m depth, only during the periods with high waterflow it rises higher.

After the setting the Gabčíkovo hydro-system into operation, it means after the filling up the water reservoir in October and November 1992 the

FIGURE 2

PRECIPITATION

SOIL MOISTURE CONTENT IN LAYER 0-1 m

GROUNDWATER TABLE

Mo 2

FS

RC

PDA

WP

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

groundwater table rose up to 3-2 m below the surface and since then it is stabilized in this depth.

The soil moisture content expressed in mm in the 1 m thick soil layer varies from 100 to 250 mm or in the so called semiarid moisture interval, i.e. between the hydrolimits: Point of decreased soil water availability (PDA) and Wilting point (WP).

This situation is preserved also after the groundwater table rise (in year 1993) Reason is the low capillary rise in the sandy substrate in the depth of 2-3 m.

2.2. Area with assumed fall of the groundwater table

The measurement showed that the prognosed fall of the groundwater table to the depth of 3-4 m was not confirmed and is preserved in the original depth 1-2 m also after the hydro-system realization (in year 1993).

Soil moisture content in 1 m thick soil layer varies between 350-400 mm. It is between hydrolimits: Retention capacity (RC) and Point of decreased soil water availability (PDA), i.e. semiuidic moisture interval. This moisture interval is most favourable for plant growth as it offers the optimal water supply and sufficient aeration for the plant roots.

2.3. Area without groundwater table changes

Data obtained on the monitoring plot Mp 16 (Figure 4) represent the soil moisture in the lower part of Žitný ostrov where no changes were presumed. The situation is similar as in the previous area. The groundwater table is preserved in original depth 2-3m. The soil moisture content falls in summer months from semiuidic to semiarid moisture interval.

3. CONCLUSION

The present results of the groundwater table and soil moisture monitoring allows to presume, that the prognosed negative influence of the hydro-sys-

tem Gabčíkovo on the soil are not confirmed. The groundwater levels and soil moisture regime are preserved in the original state. All other soil properties should be preserved without changes.

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Name und Anschrift des Verfassers:

Emil FULAJTÁR st.
Soil Fertility Research Institute
Gagarinova 10
827 13 Bratislava
Slovak Republic

TO THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN AUSTRIAN AND SLOVAKIAN SOIL SCIENTISTS

P.JAMBOR

Very close neighbourhood of our two countries enabled relatively busy contacts that have their own history beginning in old Austrian Monarchy in previous century. In this period our soil scientists (H.Horusitzky, E.Timko, etc.) working within Hungary also collaborated with austrian pedologists in the territory of Danubian Lowland, when working with agrogeological research and soil productivity potential.

Another possibility of coloboration arose during the years of second world war, when in our country appeared new generation of soil scientists headed by Pecho-Pečner - mayor of Bratislava and prominent pedologist. The other famous soil scientist in this period was O.Kožuch.

New contacts have been established during last two or three decades. During this period, in February 1964 was at our institute founded the Societas Pedologica, Slovak Republic as a branch of the International Soil Science Society with first chairman Prof. J.Hraško today Minister of Environment. We obtained very good possibilities to contact austrian pedologists and exchange experiences with them, in the fields of soil survey, research, classification and bonitation, and in region of the relation between plant and soil (e. g. sugar beet), etc. To the personalities with best relation to our country in this period belonged also Prof. J.Fink. Later in natural way were established contacts with Prof. O.Nestroy, Prof. W.Blum, Dr. H.Müller, etc.

From Slovakian side is necessary to mention activities directed to Austria from Prof. J.Hraško, Dr. M.Džatko, Dr. P.Bielek, Doc. J.Čurlík, Dr. B.Juráni, Dr. Z.Bedrna, Prof. J.Hanes, Prof. K.Holobradý, etc.

Very effective form of the information exchange has been excursion and possibility to see soils and landscape with own eyes. The Societas Pedologica twice had the pleasure to invite our austrian colleagues to see soils and landscape in southern and west part of Western Slovak Republic. And vice versa, we were highly appreciated with fantastic opportunity for us, in 5 summer days to see landscape, soils and people in eastern, northern and central parts of Austria in altitudes 130 to more than 1200 m above sea level, with soil types - Chernozems, Orthic Luvisols, Cambisols and Podzols and their subtypes. Our guide and excellent teacher was Prof.O.Nestroy.

Another type of relations had our colleagues (Doc. J.Čurlík et al.) with Agricultural University, Vienna (Dr.Rampazzo et al) in the field of physical soil properties.

We also appreciate our contacts with Prof.Blum as the ISSS secretary, as well as prominent pedological personality.

This our meeting is also a result of our mutual relations. I personally and from the position of the Societas Pedologica president am wishing all the best our meeting, you all, and I wish us future very close and fruitful collaboration.

Die unmittelbare Nachbarschaft unserer beiden Länder ermöglicht relativ intensive Kontakte, ähnlich wie sie schon während der ehemaligen Donaumonarchie bis in dieses Jahrhundert hinein bestanden haben. In dieser Zeit haben unsere Bodenkundler (H.Horusitzky, E.Timko u.a.), die in Ungarn tätig waren, mit den österreichischen Fachkollegen im Gebiet des Donautieflandes in Fragen der agraren Forschung wie der Bodenfruchtbarkeit mitgearbeitet. Eine weitere Möglichkeit der Zusammenarbeit entstand während des Zweiten Weltkrieges, als in unserem Lande eine neue Generation von Bodenkundlern unter der Führung von Pecho-Pečner, Bürgermeister von Bratislava und prominenter Bodenkundler, auf den Plan trat. Ein anderer berühmter Bodenkundler in dieser Periode war O.Kožuch.

In den letzten zwei bis drei Jahrzehnten entstanden neue Kontakte. In dieser Periode wurde im Februar 1964 in unserem Institut die Societas Pedologica,

Slovakia als nationale Gesellschaft (im Rahmen der Internationalen Bodenkundlichen Gesellschaft) mit dem jetzigen Minister für Umwelt, Herrn Univ.-Prof. J.Hraško, als den ersten Vorsitzenden gegründet. Wir hatten und haben sehr gute Möglichkeiten, mit den österreichischen Kollegen in Verbindung zu treten und Erfahrungen auszutauschen, so auf dem Gebiet der Bodensystematik, -bonitierung und des Stoffmetabolismus zwischen Pflanze und Boden. Zu jenen Persönlichkeiten mit den besten Beziehungen zu unserem Land während dieser Periode zählte Univ.-Prof.J.Fink. Später entwickelten sich ganz natürlich Kontakte mit Univ.-Prof. O.Nestroy, Univ.-Prof. W.Blum, Dr. H.Müller u.a. Von slowakischer Seite ist notwendig, die Aktivitäten in Richtung Österreich zu erwähnen, die von den Herrn Univ.-Prof. J.Hraško, Dr. M.Džatko, Dr. P.Bielek, Univ.-Doz. J.Čurlík, Dr. B.Juráni, Dr. Z.Bedrna, Univ.-Prof. J.Hanes, Univ.-Prof. K.Holobradý u.a.m. wahrgenommen werden.

Eine sehr effektive Form des Informationsaustausches waren Exkursionen und damit die Möglichkeiten, Böden und Landschaft mit eigenen Augen zu sehen. Die Societas Pedologica hatte zweimal die Freude, die österreichischen Kollegen in Ihrem Lande begrüßen zu können und ihnen die Landschaften der Süd- und Westslowakei zu zeigen. Vice versa, wir schätzen uns sehr glücklich über die phantastische Gelegenheit im Rahmen einer 5tägigen Exkursion Böden und Leute in Teile Niederösterreichs, der Steiermark und des Burgenlandes, in Höhen von 130 bis 1.200 m über dem Meere kennenzulernen und Tschernoseme, Luvisole, Cambisole und ihren Untertypen zu sehen. Unser Begleiter und vorzüglicher Lehrer war O.Nestroy.

Beziehungen anderer Art haben unsere Kollegen (Univ.-Doz.J.Čurlík u.a.) mit der Universität für Bodenkultur in Wien (mit Dr. N.Rampazzo u.a.) auf dem Gebiet der physikalischen Eigenschaften der Böden.

Wir schätzen auch unsere Kontakte mit Univ.-Prof. W.Blum, dem Sekretär der ISSS und prominente pedologische Persönlichkeit.

Dieses Zusammentreffen ist ein Resultat unserer gegenseitigen Beziehungen. Ich persönlich und auch in meiner Eigenschaft als Präsident der Societas Pedologica, wünsche diesem Treffen und Ihnen alles Gute - auch für eine weitere, fruchtbare Zusammenarbeit.

Dobré susedské vzťahy našich dvoch krajín umožnili vznik živých kontaktov, ktorých história siaha ďaleko do časov Monarchie v osemnástom a deväťnástom storočí. Asi uprostred tohoto obdobia pôdoznalci slovenského pôvodu (H. Hurusitzky, E. Timko a iní), ktorí boli činní v rámci Uhorska, tiež úzko spolupracovali s pôdoznalcami z oblasti rakúskej časti Podunajskej nížiny, v oblasti agroekologického výskumu a produkčného potenciálu pôdy.

Iná možnosť spolupráce sa vytvorila v čase rokov druhej svetovej vojny, keď v našej krajine pracovala nová generácia pôdoznalcov, do čela ktorej sa postavil Pecho-Pečner - starosta Bratislavy a známy pôdoznalec. Iný známy slovenský pôdoznalec tohoto obdobia bol O. Kožuch.

Nové kontakty vznikali v čase posledných dvoch, či troch desaťročí, keď nastúpila umiernennejšia fáza socialistického režimu u nás. Na začiatku tohoto obdobia, vo februári 1964 bola pri našom ústave (vtedy Laboratórium pôdoznalectva) založená Societas Pedologica, ako pobočka Medzinárodnej pôdoznaleckej spoločnosti a do jej čela sa postavil vtedy Ing. J. Hraško, CSc., dnes minister životného prostredia SR. Získali sme veľmi dobré možnosti komunikovať s rakúskymi pôdoznalcami a vymieňať si s nimi skúsenosti v oblasti pôdneho prieskumu a výskumu, pôdnej klasifikácie a bonitácie a v oblasti vzťahov medzi rastlinou a pôdou (napr. pri cukrovej repe) atď. K osobnostiam s najlepším vzťahom k našej krajine patrili Prof. Julius Fink. Neskôr prirodzeným spôsobom sa vytvorili kontakty s Prof. O. Nestroyom, Prof. Blumom, Dr. Müllerom a inými.

Zo slovenskej strany sa musíme zmieniť o aktivitách smerovaných na Rakúsko, ktoré vyvíjali hlavne Prof. Hraško, Dr. Džatko, Dr. Bielek, Doc. Čurlík, Dr. Juráni, Dr. Bedrna, Prof. Hanes, Prof. Holobradý a iní.

Veľmi efektívnou formou výmeny informácií je, okrem iného, aj exkurzia a možnosť vidieť pôdy a krajinu na vlastné oči. Naša Societas Pedologica dvakrát privítala rakúskych kolegov pri exkurzii na pôdy a do krajiny v južnej a západnej časti Záposlovenského kraja. A opačne, my sme s radosťou uvítali peknú možnosť v priebehu 5 letných dní vidieť pôdy, krajinu a ľudí v severných a stredných častiach Rakúska v rozmedzí nadmorskej výšky 130 až

1200 m nad morom s pôdnymi typmi černoze, hnedoze, kambize a podzoly a ich subtypy. Naším sprievodcom a výborným učiteľom pritom bol Prof. Nestroy.

Iným typom vzájomných vzťahov je oblasť odbornej spolupráce napr. v oblasti pôdnej fyziky s Poľnohospodárskou univerzitou vo Viedni (Doc. J. Čurlík et al - Dr.M. Rampazzo et al.).

Tiež si vysoko ceníme naše kontakty s Prof. Blumom ako tajomníkom ISSS a známou osobnosťou v oblasti pedológie.

Nedá mi, aby som nespomenul, že začiatky vzájomných kontaktov, veľmi plodných môžeme hľadať už za Márie Terézie, kedy bol vypracovaný prvý bonitačný systém pôd, nami používaný ešte v predchádzajúcom desaťročí.

Toto naše stretnutie je tiež výsledkom našich vzájomných vzťahov, nás prítomných na tomto stretnutí.

Ja osobne a tiež z pozície predsedu Societas Pedologica prajem nášmu stretnutiu to najlepšie a nám všetkým do budúcnosti veľmi úzku a plodnú spoluprácu.

Name und Anschrift des Verfassers:

Pavel JAMBOR

Soil Fertility Research Institute

Gagarinova 10

827 13 Bratislava

Slovak Republic

SLOVAK REPUBLIC SOILS MONITORING SYSTEM

V.LINKEŠ

SUMMARY

A monitoring and information system is of great importance, particularly in the countries with very heterogenous soil cover. The Slovak Soil Information System includes, as a great part, the pedological survey results that started in 1961. These data are divided in following data bases:

1. data basis 17 000 analysed soil profiles;
2. data basis 300 complexly analysed soil profiles;
3. data basis 490 analysed soil profiles within farming land hygienic survey (2M HNO₃, extractable risk element contents);
4. monitoring soil network data basis from 1993 that consists of 601 soil profiles (280 soil profiles of farming land, and 338 soil profiles of forest land);
5. trace element soil profile data basis of the mapping network 10x10 km - their total contents in Slovak Republic soils (Geochemical Atlas).

Finally come the impulse for information profile network generation at farming land with density nearly 1/700 ha, including trace element contents in soil, and on the other hand information network with density 1/120 ha including values of basic soil properties.

Information system cartographical network is composed of digitalized map databases - so called pedo-ecological units (lowest taxonomical units of soil classification with the categories of sloppiness and climatic regions) in scale 1:5000. This data basis is using the software of geochemical system IGIS,

with possible export to the system ARC/INFO. The soil Monitoring System concept includes following stages:

1. Soil and Plant risk element contents survey (total contents and 2M HNO₃ extractable contents);
2. Detailed investigation of the soil contamination in the "hot spot" regions;
3. Natural geochemical anomalies separation that are occurring in Slovak Republic in relatively high rate;
4. Monitoring soil network construction (618 locations), with the monitoring of basic soil property changes. It is assumed that there will be used deluometrical measurement and remote sensing for erosion monitoring;
5. Construction of the key location network (10 - 115) with annual monitoring of the soil property changes, with soil inputs.

The Soil Monitoring Information System is integral part of the Environment Information System in Slovak Republic.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Speziell in einem Gebiet mit einer heterogenen Bodendecke haben Bodeninformationen und Bodenmonitoringinformationssysteme eine große Bedeutung. Das Bodeninformationssystem der Slowakei besteht aus einer großen Zahl von pedologischen Übersichtsdaten ab dem Jahre 1961.

Folgende Datenbanken stehen zur Verfügung:

1. Datenbasis von 17.000 analysierten Bodenprofilen.
2. Datenbasis von 300 komplett analysierten Bodenprofilen.
3. Datenbasis von 4990 analysierten Bodenprofilen im System der hygienischen Übersicht von landwirtschaftlich genutzten Böden (Gehalt an gesundheitsgefährdenden Stoffen).
4. Datenbasis der Bodenmonitoringnetzwerks ab dem Jahre 1993, das aus 601 Bodenprofilen besteht (280 Bodenprofile von landwirtschaftlich, 338 Profile von forstlich genutzten Böden).

5. Datenbasis des Bodenprofile im Netzwerk 10 x 10 km für die Erfassung der Gesamtgehalte an Spurenelementen in den Böden der Slowakei (Geochemischer Atlas).

Schließlich entsteht ein Informationsnetzwerk von Bodenprofilen landwirtschaftlich genutzter Flächen in der Dichte von einem Profil für 700 Hektar einschließlich der Spurenelementgehalte der Böden, ferner ein Informationsnetzwerk in der Dichte von einem Profil für 200 Hektar mit den Daten über die pedologischen Grundeigenschaften.

Der graphische Teil des Bodeninformationssystems besteht aus digitalisierten Datebasiskarten, den sogenannten ökologischen Bodeneinheiten (die niedrigste taxonomische Einheit der Bodenklasifikation mit Angaben über Neigung und über die klimatischen regionalen Kategorien im Maßstab 1:5.000).

Diese Datenbasis stützt sich auf das geographische System IGIS mit der Möglichkeit, Daten in das ARC/INFO-System zu exportieren.

Im Bodenmonitoringsystem sind folgende Informationen gespeichert:

1. Übersicht über die Gehalte an gefährlichen Stoffen in Böden und Pflanzen (2M HNO₃-Auszug und Gesamtbestimmung).
2. Detaillierte Untersuchungen über die Bodenverunreinigung in den "hot spot" Regionen.
3. Ausgrenzung der natürlichen geochemischen Anomalien in der Slowakei.
4. Darstellung des Bodenmonitoringnetzwerks (618 Standorte) mit den zeitlichen Bodenveränderungen. Deluoumetrische Messungen und Daten der Fernerkundung wurden für die Erosionsforschung herangezogen.
5. Darstellung eines Netzwerks der Hauptstandorte (10 bis 15) mit den jährlich gemessenen Veränderungen des Inputs und der Bodeneigenschaften.

Das Bodenmonitoring-Informationssystem ist ein Teil des Umweltinformationssystems der Slowakei.

S Ú H R N

System informácií a monitoringu má veľkú dôležitosť, najmä v krajinách s veľmi heterogénnym pôdnym pokryvom.

Pôdny informačný systém na Slovensku sa skladá z veľkej časti z výsledkov pedologického prieskumu, ktorý sa začal v roku 1961. Tieto údaje sú zaradené do nasledujúcich databáz:

1. databáza 17 000 analyzovaných pôdných profilov
2. databáza 300 komplexne analyzovaných pôdných profilov
3. databáza 490 analyzovaných pôdných profilov v rámci hygienického prieskumu poľnohospodárskych pôd (2M HNO₃, extrahovateľný obsah rizikových prvkov)
4. databáza monitorovacej pôdnej siete z r. 1993, ktorá sa skladá z 601 pôdných profilov (280 pôdných profilov poľnohospodárskych pôd a 338 pôdných profilov lesných pôd)
5. databáza pôdných profilov mapovacej siete 10x10 km stopových prvkov - ich celkový obsah v pôdach Slovenska (Geochemický atlas).

Nakoniec prišiel popud na vytvorenie informačnej siete profilov poľnohospodárskej pôdy s hustotou približne 1/700 ha vrátane hodnôt obsahu stopových prvkov v pôdach na jednej strane a na druhej strane informačná sieť s hustotou 1/120 ha vrátane hodnôt základných pôdných vlastností.

Karbografická sieť informačného systému sa skladá z databázy digitalizovaných máp - tzv. pôdno-ekologické jednotky (najnižšie taxonomické jednotky pôdnej klasifikácie s kategóriami svahovitosti a klimatických regiónov) v mierke 1:5000. Táto databáza využíva software geografického systému IGIS s možným exportom do systému ARC/INFO.

Koncepcia pôdneho monitorovacieho systému zahrňuje nasledovné štádiá:

1. Prieskum obsahu rizikových prvkov v pôdach a rastlinách (celkový obsah a 2M HNO₃ extrahovateľný obsah)

2. Podrobný výskum pôdnej kontaminácie v regiónoch "hot spots"
3. Oddelenie prírodných geochemických anomálií, ktoré sa vo veľkej miere vyskytujú na Slovensku
4. Konštrukcia pôdnej siete monitoringu (618 lokalít) s monitoringom zmien pôdnych vlastností. Predpokladá sa, že sa použijú deluometrické merania a diaľkové snímanie pre monitoring erózie.
5. Konštrukcia siete kľúčových lokalít (10-15) s ročným monitoringom zmien pôdnych vlastností spolu so vstupmi do pôdy.

Pôdny monitorovací informačný systém je časťou Informačného systému životného prostredia na Slovensku.

INTRODUCTION

Slovak Republic soil monitoring system is a part of the environmental monitoring system. The soil monitoring system is based on the network of 618 localities on the all territory of Slovak Republic (49 000 km²). The measurements of soil properties will be repeated every 3 to 5 years and in the 20 keyed localities a number of times per year and inputs to the soil system as well. The start of mentioned monitoring was 1993 year. In the first stage we investigated the state of the soil contamination and the starting points of monitored soil properties. Accordingly it is visible the soils of Slovak Republic are contaminated above hygienic limits only in the 0,6 % (in the case of Cr) to 15,5 % (in the case of Cd) from the monitoring localities. The great part of localities which are containing the trace elements above limits are in the natural geochemical anomalous areas, the other part is concentrated in the well known "hot spots" regions and significant part of the monitoring localities is in the SW Slovak Republic, where is visible the emission influence from Poland and Moravia and Silesia. Simultaneously with the realisation of soil monitoring system is creating its database and the special information system.

SOIL COVER QUALITATIVE STRUCTURE AND SOIL CONTAMINATION STATUS - MONITORING BACKGROUND

Slovak Republic soil cover is very heterogenous. Almost all soils of the temperate zone are situated in this relatively small territory. Complicated is also parent material geochemical composition, this is conditioning great variability in trace element contents, as in whole Slovak Republic territory there are numerous natural geochemical anomalies (primary locations of their occurrence and weathered material areals and soils contaminated by the fragmental ore minerals and mainly by the trace elements in ionic form).

Soil contamination surveys in various anthropogenous resources that have been proceeding in Slovak Republic for almost 20 years, show us, the territory is influenced by the anthropogenous contamination in different ways. Besides the "hot spots" regions that in comparison with considerable pollutant sources in Europe, are relatively small, the Slovak Republic territory is visibly impacted by foreign pollutant producers (particularly from western and northern industry agglomerations of Moravia and Silesia, and mainly from Poland), as well as by global pollutant transfer in higher altitudes.

The localities with soil contamination by pollutants above hygienic limits, are relatively small and their considerable part is located in geochemical anomalies.

Principles of the Slovak Republic Soil Monitoring System and its information system.

The Soil Monitoring System has been existing since 1993 (partially since 1992) monitoring system covers whole agricultural land forestry land and also the soils above upper forest limit.

Basic monitoring objective is most significant soil properties observation, as well as their contamination status (irreversible parameter changes at soil properties) in space - and time, but out of the very small soil contamination localities that are subject of hygienical control and control system of environment protection (e. g. waste dumps, etc).

Soil Monitoring Information System is collected, archived in databases, it is interpreting and presenting information for users as far as soil properties and soil contamination status concerned in the points of monitoring network localities with the GIS use. In next future there will be also presented by means of the GIS also the areals of soil contamination scale in small mapping scales. Most important users of the information on Slovak Republic soils contamination status are: food quality information system and environment protection system.

Soil Monitoring System - methodological principles

Slovak Republic Soil Monitoring System is composed of two parts:

- 1 - so called areal farming land contamination in that survey, are analyzed trace elements from the surface horizon of plots and selected organic pollutants. Contemporarily from the plots are sampled plants for food and fodder monitoring. The survey is connected also with agro-chemical soil testing on pH and available nutrients (P, K, Mg). This time it is single survey, and probably will be repeated only in areas with ascertained soil and plant contamination and in some check areas.
- 2 - Slovak Republic soil actual monitoring based on monitoring localities network with area 314 m² (at forest soils from 200 to 1000 m²). Network of the monitoring localities at farming land is not regular and includes 280 ones (1 for 80 km²) that were selected so that they characterized main soil units, main soil contamination types and main landscape use types. In the region of forest soils is monitoring localities network regular (8 x 8 km), as it is identical with the network of international forest monitoring. All the localities are geodetically identified in national coordinate system.

In every location there is pedological profile with data on soil profile stratigraphy and most important soil properties. Sampling depths for contaminant contents analyses are standard: from three depths and parent material, in for-

est soils there are also analyzed samples from the surface organic horizons. Monitoring subject are following soil properties: pH exchangeable and active, exchangeable Al, available nutrient P, K, Mg, humus content and quality, total N, exchangeable cations, physical properties (only at arable land) and soil erosion in selected localities (deloumetrically, and according vertical distribution of ^{137}Cs contents). From the contaminants the monitoring subject are total contents and their contents in 2M HNO_3 in the case of elements Cd, Pb, As, Cu, Ni, Hg, Cr, and possibly also Mn, Co, Se and others. From organic pollutants: PAH, PCB, and organic chlorinated pesticides.

Results from 1993/1994

First soil monitoring stage is focused on findings about soil characteristics parameters, and particularly on soil contamination status.

Farming land contamination status is assessed according the ranges of the trace elements contents background (95 % part of the statistical values frequency distribution) and their contents evaluation from the view point of hygienic limits (we are using contents in 2M HNO_3).

Cd range is from 0,01 to 1,83 ppm, median 0,16 ppm. Above hygienic limit (0,3 ppm) is 15,5 % localities, most in geochemical anomalies.

Pb range is from 0,3 to 80 ppm, median 13,0 ppm. Above hygienic limit (30 ppm) is 5,8 % localities, most in geochemical anomalies.

Cr range is from 0,1 to 8,25 ppm, median 2,17 ppm. Above hygienic limit (13 ppm) is 0,6 % localities in anthropogenically contaminated areas.

As range (total contents) is from 0,2 to 20 ppm, median 6,79 ppm. Above hygienic limit (17,4 to 37 ppm) is approximately 10 % localities most in anthropogenically contaminated areas, less in geochemical anomalies.

Hg ranges (total contents) is 0,02 to 0,37 ppm) is approximately 5 % localities from areas contaminated anthropogenically, as well as from geochemical anomalies.

Watersoluble F above limit contents occur only in aluminum plant Žiar nad Hronom surroundings.

Elements Co, Cu, Zn were determined in above limit amounts only in rare localities.

Trace elements contents profile distribution is expressing only very moderate increase in surface horizons, due to anthropogenous influences. In geochemical anomalies are trace elements contents higher under humus horizon, this depends from the stratigraphy evolution of soil parent materials.

From organic pollutants were in farming land determined total PAH contents in range 0,004 to 3,020 ppm. The contents above limit (1 ppm) occurred only rarely, equally also PCB contents.

Above limit soil contamination with radioactive izotopes (measured by ^{137}Cs activity) was not detected.

Name und Anschrift des Verfassers:

Vladimír LINKEŠ
Soil Fertility Research Institute
Gagarinova 10
827 13 Bratislava
Slovak Republic

THE POSITION OF SOIL ECOLOGY IN THE SCOPE OF THE ECOLOGY

O.NESTROY

SUMMARY

After one introductory definition of the concepts ecology, ecological equilibrium and ecosystem there follows a description of the status of soil ecology within the context of ecological aspects. One table demonstrate the connection between ecological parameters and disciplines. Finally the definition of soil ecology is given and a critical examination there of as a basis for further discussions.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Nach der einleitender Definition der Begriffe Ökologie, ökologisches Gleichgewicht und Ökosystem wird die Stellung der Bodenökologie im Rahmen der ökologischen Betrachtungsweisen dargestellt. Eine Tabelle verdeutlicht die Querverbindungen der ökologischen Parameter und auch Disziplinen. Schließlich wird eine Definition des Begriffs Bodenökologie gegeben und dessen kritische Beleuchtung als Auftakt für weitere Diskussionen.

SÚHRN

Po úvodnej definícii koncepcií ekológie, ekologickej rovnováhy a ekosystému nasleduje popis statútu pôdnej ekológie v kontexte s ekologickými aspektami. V tabuľke je demonštrované spojenie medzi ekologickými parametrami a disciplínami. Nakoniec je daná definícia pôdnej ekológie a jej kritické preskúšanie ako základňa pre ďalšie diskusie.

It is an honour and a pleasure for me to speak at this symposium on soil ecology and to discuss this subject with you.

I think, ecology is now a very common word, an expression that is frequently used, in newspapers, journals, on radio and television.

We can say in modification of a joke: Two years ago I didn't know what ecology was, now I am an ecologist. Almost everybody wants to talk about ecology, wants to work on ecology.

But at the beginning of this meeting it seems important to me to take some consideration about the name, the definition and the different kinds of ecology. The name ecology is taken from the Greek expression *oikos* and *logos*, which means house, and the Latin word *verbum* which can be transferred as thought, science.

The discoverer of ecology was Ernst Haeckel, who in 1886 formulated the first definition for the science concerning the connection between organisms and their biotic and abiotic environment. And Haeckel recognized not only the connection between organisms and the environment but also that this connection is an open system, it forms and it is formed by other factors.

Since that time many people have been working on ecology, and for this reason we have a lot of definitions so that it is difficult to find a suitable one. As a result of all these investigations I found a comprehensive definition which I want to use in this lecture:

"Ecology is the science on the relation between organisms and their biotic and abiotic environment, it is the structure and function of nature."

In this connection I must add the definition for ecological equilibrium:

"Ecological equilibrium is the long-term unchangeable interaction between the members of a biocoenosis."

If this equilibrium is disturbed for a long time we have a succession, a disturbance, a profound change. We just have to remember the changes of soils which have occurred under intensive and long-term human impact.

According to a proposal by A. Tansley (1935) ecosystem is an expression for a biocoenosis and its biotops. We see the ecological unity and a more or

less constant system in the interactions between organisms and environmental factors, such as for example in a lake, in bogland, a beech-forest, a coast and a riff.

In this sense and following F. Schwerdtfeger (1963), we can define ecosystem as follow:

"Ecosystem is every kind of ecological structure, a partnership between organisms and the various factors of the environment."

Ecology can thus be regarded as the most complex discipline of biology.

For this reason we can observe many sections, many branches of ecology, depending on the-point-of-view (see table 1).

This table is only a proposal for one systematic and logical order. This paper and this basis for discussion is not in contradiction with the existing concepts. The factors can be geofactors (rock, relief, climate) or biofactors (plant, animal and man), and the link between the two categories is soil. With regard to functions we can distinguish several systems (morpho-, hydro-, pedosystems, phytocoenosis and zoocoenosis, further social and/or economic systems). The topes include the morpho-, hydro-, pedo-, phyto-, and zootope, further the living space and the radius of human actions.

Finally we can speak of an ecological research discipline. Every discipline is a complex result of all factors from a special point-of-view. Landscape ecology focuses on morphology, however, taking into conderation also the other factors. In this column we find also the soil ecology, further phyto ecology, ecological geobotanics, zoo ecology, human ecology, social ecology and, with some distance, agrarian ecology.

For soil ecology, we can find the following definition:

"Soil ecology is the science about the relation of the organisms and their biotic and abiotic environment in the area of soil in a biological sense".

As far so good - but it isn't the end of this reflection.

Table 1

Ecological aspects

Factors ("who" or "what")		Functions ("how")	Unit of space ("where")	Ecological research discipline	
Geofactors	Biofactors	morphosystem	morphotop	landscape ecology,	
rock		hydrosystem	hydrotop		scenic eco- logy
relief		pedosystem	pedotop	soil ecology	
climate					phytocoenosis
		soil	zoocoenosis	zootop	zoo ecology
		plant	social and/or economic system	living space, ra- dius of action (region, environ- ment)	human (anthro- po) ecology, social ecology
	animal				
	man			agrarian ecology	

Professor J. V. Ottow from the institute of Microbiology of the Justus-von-Liebig-Universität Gießen, Germany, writes in his most recent paper (Symposium of Soil Microbiology in Linz, Austria, 1993) entitled: Microbiology in Germany: Besides the ecology of plants and zoos or the ecology of microorganisms it is not possible that there exists a soil ecology, because soils are themselves products of the reciprocal actions between organisms and soil

matrix. The term soil ecology is only an excuse which allows us to deal with questions of soil ecology without admitting the central role of organisms. I cannot myself understand this statement because all soil scientists know that soil and soil ecology are a complex system, which is guided by abiotic and biotic factors, forming and formed by the other factors, which are part of the abiotic and biotic environment.

This is my credo and this is my proposal for future discussions.

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Name und Anschrift des Verfassers:

O.NESTROY

Institut für Technische Geologie und Angewandte Mineralogie an der
Technischen Universität Graz

Rechbauerstraße 12

A-8010 Graz

Austria

**SOIL STRUCTURE ASSESSMENT-
THE IMPORTANCE OF MINERALOGICAL AND
MICROMORPHOLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS**

N. RAMPAZZO, W.E.H. BLUM, J. ČURLÍK

SUMMARY

Status and stability of the soil structure are influenced by various chemical, physical, mineralogical and biological parameters, depending on natural and anthropogenic factors. Soil mineralogy and soil micromorphology are closely related to the structural status of soils and contribute to understand the soil structure per se and its functionality within a soil profile. Soil mineralogy describes the composition of the inorganic solid phase. Soil micromorphology describes not only soil components, soil features and phenomena at a microscopically scale but also their organization within the pedon. As an example, the structure of 3 different soil was investigated using mineralogical and micromorphological methods.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Natürliche und anthropogene Faktoren beeinflussen den Zustand und die Stabilität der Bodenstruktur durch Veränderung verschiedener chemischer, physikalischer, mineralogischer und biologischer Parameter. Die Bodenmineralogie und -mikromorphologie sind zwei von mehreren Gruppen von Strukturparametern, die notwendig sind, um den Zustand und die Funktionalität des Gefüges eines Bodens zu verstehen. Während die Bodenmineralogie die Zusammensetzung der festen anorganischen Phase beschreibt, untersucht

die Bodenmikromorphologie nicht nur einzelne Bodenkomponenten und -merkmale, sondern auch deren Organisation innerhalb eines Bodens. Als Beispiel wird in dieser Arbeit die Struktur dreier verschiedener Böden mittels mineralogischer und mikromorphologischer Methoden untersucht.

S Ú H R N

Stav a stabilita pôdnej štruktúry sú ovplyvňované rôznymi chemickými, fyzikálnymi a biologickými parametrami v závislosti na prírodných a antropogénnych faktoroch. Pôdna mineralógia a pôdna mikromorfológia sú v úzkom vzťahu so štruktúrnym zložením pôd a prispievajú k chápaniu pôdnej štruktúry ako takej, jej funkčnosti v rámci pôdneho profilu. Pôdna mineralógia popisuje zloženie anorganickej pôdnej fázy. Pôdna mikromorfológia popisuje nie iba pôdne zložky, pôdne črty a javy v mikroskopickom merítku, ale tiež ich organizáciu v rámci pedónu. Príkladom môže byť štruktúra 3 odlišných pôd, ktoré boli študované za použitia mineralogických a mikromorfologických metód.

INTRODUCTION

Soil structure can be defined as *the physical constitution of solid soil materials as expressed by the size, shape and arrangement of the solid particles and voids, including both the primary and newly formed particles. The soil fabric is the element of the soil structure, which deals with the particle arrangement.*

The solid soil phase consists of coarse clastogene (detrital) components, which are inherited from parent rocks or sediment (so-called "primary" minerals) and fine (colloidal) minerals, which can be inherited, transformed and or neofomed in the soils (pedogenetical "secondary" neofomation such as clay minerals, carbonates, sulphates, sesquioxides, salts), as a consequence of weathering and transport processes. The distribution of minerals in soils is in some way related to the particle size distribution. "Primary" coarse

minerals are mostly concentrated in the sand fraction (2000 μm to 50 μm), whereas the secondary minerals accumulate in the silt (50 μm to 2 μm) and especially in the clay fraction (2 μm).

"Primary" minerals play an important role in the formation of soil structure by influencing the distribution of coarse pores (e.g. soil aeration and water infiltration), especially if the degree of aggregation is rather low. Moreover, the chemistry of primary minerals also influences the long-term release of ions.

The most abundant "secondary" neoformation in soils are clay minerals and Fe, AL and Mn oxides. Clay minerals influence many pedological processes because of their

- a) net negative permanent electrical layer charge due to isomorphous substitution in the tetrahedra and in the octahedra;
- b) their small particle size, high specific surface, (especially the "internal" surface of the interlayers of expandible clay minerals), high CEC, high water and cation adsorption capacity;
- c) as a consequence of water ad-/desorption, clay minerals are responsible for the plasticity, swelling and shrinking of soils.

Pedogenic ("secondary") Fe minerals (oxides, oxyhydroxides, and hydroxides) cause the hues between red and yellowish-red of most soils and their presence and abundance reflect the pedo-environmental conditions under which they have formed. They play the role of cementing agents and can stabilize the soil structure. Like in clay minerals, Fe oxides are mainly present as very fine particles in the clay fraction and have the following properties relevant to soils:

- a) On the hydroxylated or hydrated surface, a positive or negative charge is created by adsorption or desorption of H^+ or OH^- . Because of its dependence on pH and ionic strength, this type of charge is called *variable charge*.

- b) Fe oxides also adsorb a wide range of organic compounds. Humic compounds such as humic (HA) and fulvic (FA) acids may be concentrated in Fe-oxide-rich horizons of soils under humid temperate conditions, such as Bs-horizons of Podzols. The amount of adsorbed FA and HA strongly increases with decreasing pH.
- c) Fe oxides usually are believed to act as binding agents among other soil particles. This may result in cementation or aggregation of primary soil particles into larger units.

Soil micromorphology deals with the qualitative and quantitative analysis of undisturbed soil samples usually in thin sections and far less in polishing blocks (thick sections), using microscopic and submicroscopic techniques. Soil micromorphology is an indispensable tool for the interpretation of the soil structure. The set of interactions between mineralogical, chemical and biological factors is resulting in soil features which are important for the interpretation and evaluation of the soil structure. Among them, shape and size of peds, porosity, types of voids, grade of structure, pedo-features (textural, crystalline pedo-features, fabric, depletions, excrement are of main interest.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Investigated soils

In this study the following soils were discussed: a Cambisol in Austria, a Solonetz in Hungary, and an Orthic Luvisol in Poland, (FAO-classification system, 1988).

Analytical methods

The bulk soils were air-dried and sieved at 2 mm mesh size (=fine earth). For micromorphological analyses KUBIENA-boxes (10x10 cm) were used.

Mineralogical analyses:

- Semiquantitative analysis of untextured soil powder patterns and of textured clay patterns by X-ray diffraction.
- Determination of Na-dithionite-citrate-bicarbonate (DCB)-soluble, NH_4^+ - oxalatesoluble and Na-pyrophosphate-soluble contents of Fe according to SCHWERTMANN (1959 and 1964).

Micromorphological analyses

For the preparation of thick sections vertical samples were taken in 8.5x9x4 cm metal containers. After drying in room temperature over 3 months, the samples were impregnated with a polyester resin solution. The impregnation occurred in vacuum device at constant vacuum (30 hPa for about 24-36 hours). The solid phase of the soil appears white on the photographs and the resin filled pores are black.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

AUSTRIA

Mineralogical data

In the top horizons of the Cambisol a slight acidification led to a relative accumulation of quartz, feldspar and layer silicates, whereas in the parent material also calcite and dolomite were traced, s Tab. 1. The complete absence of expandible minerals of the smectite and vermiculite group has to be stressed, thus explaining the relatively low CEC and the reduced swelling and shrinking capacity, s. Tab. 2. Tab. 3. shows a typical vertical decrease of Fe oxides and no indication of alleviation.

Table 1: Semiquantitative mineralogical composition of the fine earth of the Austrian soil in weight %.

Horiz./ cm	quartz	layer- silicates	felspars	calcite	dolomite
<u>Cambisol</u>					
Ap (0-20)	42	48	10	0	0
AB (20-40)	44	41	15	0	0
Bv (40-80)	44	39	15	0	2
Bc (80-95)	33	32	6	12	17
C (95 +)	33	28	4	17	18

Table 2: Semiquantitative clay mineral distribution in the fine of the Austrian soil in weight %

Horiz./ cm	illite	vermiculite	smectite	chlorite	kaolinite
<u>Cambisol</u>					
Ap (0-20)	79	0	0	16	5
AB (20-40)	69	0	0	20	11
Bv (40-80)	77	0	0	17	6
BC (80-95)	72	0	0	20	8
C (95 *)	70	0	0	19	11

Table 3: Dithionite- (d), oxalate- (o) and pyrophos-phate- (p) soluble contents of Fe of the Austrian soil in mg/kg fine earth.

Horiz./ cm	Fe _d	Fe _o	Fe _p
<u>Cambisol</u>			
Ap (0-20)	11195	3427	760
Ab (20-40)	10310	3424	762
Bv (40-80)	9730	2896	495
BC (80-95)	8975	1641	90
C (95 +)	8195	738	39

Micromorphological data (fig. 1)

Ap-horizon, (0-20 cm):

Subangular blocky (to prismatic) microstructure. The solid material is divided into subangular aggregates which are separated by planar voids, but vughs and small channels are often present. Some parallel aligned planar voids give the structure a slightly prismatic appearance. Peds are fully or partially accommodated.

AB-horizon, (20-40 cm):

Integrain channel microstructure. Closely packed mineral grains (sand and silt) between which, in addition to the normal simple packing voids, there is a system of channels. Channels mostly elongated with usually smoothed walls. Few chambers.

Bv-horizon, (40-80 cm), and C-horizon, (95+ cm):

Massive, coherent microstructure with no discrete peds and few voids.

Fig. 1: Soil thick sections (polish blocks) of the Cambisol in Austrian at natural size.

HUNGARY

Mineralogy data

The salt-affected, ameliorated Solonetz has a very high clay content (. 50 %) and very strongly developed swelling/shrinking properties.

Micromorphological data (fig. 2.)

A-horizon, (0-20 cm):

Subangular blocky microstructure. The solid material is divided into subangular aggregates separated by short planar voids on all or most sides. Vughs and channels occur within the aggregates. The aggregate faces largely accommodate each other.

B-horizon, (20-60 cm), and BC-horizon, (60-70 cm):

Prismatic microstructure. The solid material is divided into prism separated by vertically aligned planar voids. The faces of the aggregates normally accommodate each other.

C-horizon, (70+ cm):

Subangular blocky microstructure. The solid material is divided into subangular aggregates separated by short planar voids on all or most sides. Vughs and channels occur within the aggregates. The aggregate faces largely accommodate each other.

Fig. 2: Soil thick sections (polish blocks) of the Solonetz in Hungary at natural size.

POLAND

Mineralogical data

Table 4 and shows very clearly the dynamic of clay alleviation due to pH variation. In the topsoil only quartz and feldspar are present, whereas in the Bt-horizon phyllosilicates accumulate. An accumulation of smectite in the Bt-horizon is visible, where the contents of illite and chlorite are much lower, s. Tab. 5. Smectite clay minerals are generally known to be alleviated because of their capacity of dispersion in the soil solution and their small particle size. The alleviation process also regards Fe oxides, which are accumulated in the Bt-horizon, as well, s. Tab. 6. Moreover, the Bt-horizon of Luvisols is somewhat a "weathering"-horizon. This explains the lower Fe_o/Fe_d-ratio of the Bt₁ -horizon.

Table 4: Semiquantitative mineralogical composition of the fine earth of the polish soil in weight %.

Horiz./ cm	quartz silicates	layer-	felspars	calcite	dolomite
Orthic Luvisol					
Ah	68	0	32	0	0
E	71	0	29	0	0
Bt ₁	58	39	3	0	0
Bt ₂	71	22	7	0	0
BC	61	31	8	0	0
Cca	59	20	10	7	4

Tab. 5: Semiquantitative clay mineral distribution in the fine earth of the polish soil in weight %.

Horiz.	illite	chlorite	smestite	vermiculite	kaolinite
<u>Orthic Luvisol</u>					
Ah	38	44	18	0	0
E	46	54	Tr.	0	0
Bt1	24	30	46	0	0
Bt2	31	17	52	0	0
BC	58	18	24	0	0
Cca	54	13	33	0	0

Tab. 6: Dithionite-(d), oxalate-(o) and pyrophosphate-(p) soluble contents of Fe of the polish soil in mg/kg fine earth.

Horiz.	Fed	Feo	Fep	Feo /Fed
<u>Orthic Luvisol</u>				
Ah	3520	1895	1660	53.8
E	3500	1795	1290	51.3
Bt1	6810	1848	589	27.1
Bt2	3430	1298	336	37.8
BC	3930	1210	347	30.8
Cca	2010	685	93	34.1

Micromorphological data (fig. 3.)

Ah-horizon, (0-6 cm):

The upper 3 cm are leaves and twigs, partly decomposed. The rest of the section shows a massive, coherent structure with no peds, but visible root channels and voids.

E-horizon, (6-27 cm):

Massive, coherent microstructure with no peds and few voids.

Bt1 -horizon, (27-57 cm):

Cracky microstructure with no fully separated aggregates. The matrix material is dense, but with enough chambers and voids.

BC-horizon, (105-136 cm):

This horizon shows a transition between crackly and coherent microstructure, with few, but strongly developed cracks.

Cca-horizon, (136+ cm):

Massive, dense, coherent microstructure with few, if any, voids.

Fig. 3: Soil thick sections (polish blocks) of the Luvisol in Poland at natural size.

CONCLUSIONS

The coarse "primary" soil minerals accumulate mostly in the sand and silt fraction. Besides their influence on chemical soil parameters (pH, cation re-

lease, CEC, etc.), their size, shape and arrangement seems to characterize particular types of soil macrostructure. As an example, soil horizons with massive, coherent structure are mostly sandy/silty horizons, with few or no swelling clay minerals (e.g. the C-horizon of the Cambisol in Austria, the alluvial E-horizon of the Orthic Luvisol in Poland). These horizons possess few voids, if any, and become very compact and dense when moistened. On the contrary, soils with abundant amounts of clay minerals, especially of the swelling type (smectite, randomly interstratified illite), have a very pronounced swelling/shrinking behaviour. This leads mostly to a typical cracky, prismatic macrostructure, as shown for example in the heavy-textured Solonetz of Hungary.

The *degree of crystallinity* reflects the conditions under which Fe-oxide crystals develop, and may therefore be regarded as an indicator of the pedo-environment. The degree of weathering of parent material is estimated by the ratio of DCB-soluble-Fe to total Fe (F_{DCB}/F_{total}). The ratio oxalate-soluble-Fe to dithionite-soluble Fe (F_{ox}/F_{dith}), moreover, gives a further indication of the "pedogenical" weathering intensity.

Aggregation is probably less due to crystal growth but more to the attraction between positively charged Fe oxide particles and negatively charged matrix particles, particularly clay silicates. Because the charge of Fe oxide particles is pH-dependent, their aggregation effect is also pH-dependent. Fe oxides are the more effective in aggregating silty, e.g. loessial soils, the lower their crystallinity and the higher their oxalate solubility (i.e. the higher their F_{ox}/F_{total} ratio).

The soil structure is the dynamic result of the activity of abiotic factors and processes. Usually texture, mineral composition and organic matter are the main *structure-forming factors*, together with human activities (KOOISTRA, 1991). *Structure-forming processes*, instead, determine types, size, grade, porosity, packing and stability of soil structure. Soil structure, together with soil organisms and plants, plays a main role in transport of water, gas and heat, which are *structure-following processes* (KOOISTRA, 1991). Soil micro-

morphology gives the possibility to identify the coagulating and cementing effect of components, the properties and occurrence of peds. Some of these components can be quantified in a global (porosity, volume fraction of homogeneous zones) as well as in the feature-specific sense (informations about individual objects).

The primary goal of micromorphological investigations should not only be the study of soil structure "per se", but rather its functionality within the pedon and/or at greater scale. In this respect soil micromorphology offers the opportunity of "seeing" many details, which are not recognizable with the naked eye.

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Name und Anschrift der Verfasser:

Nicola RAMPAZZO, Winfried E.H. BLUM, Peter STRAUSS
Institute of Soil Research, University of Agriculture
Gregor-Mendel-Straße 33
A-1180 Vienna
Austria

**WATER REGIME OF THE SOILS WITH DEEP GROUNDWATER LEVEL
(UPPER ŽITNÝ OSTROV) SOIL UNIT: CALCARIC FLUVISOL**

B. ŠURINA

SUMMARY

For one-day soil science excursion were - from soil geographical point of view - selected and elaborated three soil profiles. First of them (Devínska Nová Ves) demonstrates soil development connections on mindell terraces of river Danube along both sides of the boundary between Slovak Republic and Austria. The next two are as an example of typical soil development from younger (Hamuliakovo) and from older (Gabčíkovo) alluvial sediments of river Danube in Žitný Ostrov region and as the example of the influence of the ground water table on this development, too.

The soil profile is characterised by the soil horizon descriptions and by their basic analytical data (particle size distribution, agrochemical properties, sorption properties, physical properties, humus content and its quality). To the soil data of Žitný Ostrov, where occurred the changes of ground water table dynamics as a result of the hydro-power station Gabčíkovo, are enclosed graphical data about water and soil moisture regime and its changes during last years, too.

Water regime of the soils with deep ground water level is characteristic for the Upper Žitný ostrov soils, ground water level is 5 - 6 m, graphical balance of it is in Fig. 1 and 2. It is typical with all soil water zones occurrence. Zone of evaporation and transpiration that together form rooting zone, is reaching depth 1.7 m. Transition zone is divided to dotation zone (1.7 - 3.5 m) and

zone of low ground water supply (3.5 - 4.5 - 5.0 m). Capillary zone is visible above ground water level. After the Danube gate building and ground water level increase to approximately 3 m under surface the capillary zone fused with transition zone.

From the view of hydrological classification is here inleachable water regime type. From the aspect of ecological assessment soil moisture of the one meter surface layer is in semi-arid moisture interval (qZP-qV) that does not supply plants with necessary water amount.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Für eine eintägige bodenkundliche Exkursion wurden nach bodengeographischen Gesichtspunkten drei Bodenprofile ausgewählt und beschrieben. Das erste demonstriert die Zusammenhänge der Bodenentwicklung beiderseits der slowakisch-österreichischen Grenze auf mindelzeitlichen Terrassen der Donau (Devínska Nová Ves).

Die nächsten zwei Profile sind typische Beispiele für die Bodenentwicklung auf den jüngeren (Gabčíkovo) und älteren (Hamuliakovo) alluvialen Sedimenten der Donau im Gebiet von Žitný ostrov unter Grundwassereinfluß.

Die Bodenprofile werden entsprechend ihren Horizonte beschrieben und die analytischen Daten über Textur, physikalische und chemische Eigenschaften sowie Humusart und -menge sind beigefügt.

Die Angaben von Žitný ostrov sind, wo es durch die Anlage des Kraftwerks Gabčíkovo zu Änderungen des Grundwasserregimes gekommen ist, durch graphische Daten ergänzt, welche dazu beitragen, die Änderungen des Feuchte-regimes in den Böden und des Untergrundes zu verdeutlichen.

SÚHRN

Pre jednodňovú pôdoznaleckú exkurziu boli z pôdno-geografického hľadiska vybrané a spracované tri pôdne profily. Prvý demonštruje návaznosť vývoja pôd po oboch stranách Slovensko-Rakúskej hranice na mindeliských terasách

Dunaja (Devínska Nová Ves). Ďalšie dva sú príkladom typického vývoja pôd na mladších (Hamuliakovo) a starších (Gabčíkovo) aluviálnych sedimentoch Dunaja v oblasti Žitného - ostrova a vplyvu hladiny podzemnej vody na tento vývoj.

Pôdny profil je charakterizovaný popisom pôdnych horizontov a ich základnými analytickými údajmi (textúra, agrochemické vlastnosti, sorpčné vlastnosti, fyzikálne vlastnosti, obsah humusu a jeho kvalita). K údajom o pôdach Žitného ostrova, kde došlo v dôsledku vybudovania vodného diela Gabčíkovo ku zmenám dynamiky hladín podzemnej vody, sú priložené tiež grafické údaje o vodnom a vlhkosťnom režime pôd a podložia a o dynamike ich zmien v posledných rokoch.

WATER REGIME OF THE SOILS WITH HIGH GROUND WATER LEVEL (ČILIŽSKÁ MOKRAĎ) SOIL UNIT: FLUVI-CALCARIC PHAEOZEM

Water regime of the soils with high ground water level is characteristic for depression locations of Medium Žitný ostrov, ground water depth is 1.2 - 2 m, graphically it is balanced in Fig. 3 and 4. The soil unit is typical with relatively shallow transpiration zone (0.8 m), here is attached capillary zone supplying the transpiration zone by sufficient amount of soil water.

From the view of hydrological classification is here water regime of evaporation type. According ecological criteria water regime is favourable. Moisture is in optimum semi-uvudic interval, whereby plants are sufficiently supplied by easily available water and contemporarily they have sufficient amount of air. Profile No.: 1

Profile No.: 1

Location: *Devínska Nová Ves*
 Soil unit - M.S.C.S.: *Černozem kambizemná - ČMk*
 - F.A.O.: *Cambic Chernozem - Cc*
 Parent material: *Sandy-gravel terrace material*
 Physiography: *South slope of dissected mindell terrace*
 Land use: *Arable land*
 Altitude: *149 m*

Soil description:

Amčp - 10YR 3/3 (0-28 cm) moist matrix colour, sandy loam texture, some gravels, weak grade crumb to subangular blocky structure, firm consistence, without lime, many roots, clear smooth boundary to

Amč - 10YR 3/3 (28-45 cm) moist matrix colour, sandy loam texture, 20 % gravels, weak grade crumb to subangular blocky structure, firm consistence, out lime, common roots, gradual boundary to

ABv/C - 10YR 4/4 (45-60 cm) moist matrix colour, sandy loam texture, 30 % gravels, subangular blocky structure, firm to very firm consistence, without lime, few roots, gradual boundary to

C₁ - 10YR 6/3 (>60 cm) moist matrix colour, loamy sand texture, 40 % gravels, weak grade subangular blocky structure, firm consistence, without roots.

Some analytical data of the profile No. 1

Horizon	Depth in cm	Particle size distribution (mm) in %						Humus %	pH		CEC (mval/ 100 g)	Base sat. %	CaCO ₃ %
		<0.01	<0.001	0.001- -0.01	0.01- -0.05	0.05- -0.25	0.25- -2.0		H ₂ O	KCl			
Amčp	0-28	19.8	7.5	12.3	19.2	41.3	19.7	2.14	7.2	6.6	11.6	91.4	0
Amč	28-45	19.0	8.8	10.2	17.4	45.3	18.3	1.71	7.1	6.5	9.1	97.8	0
ABv/C	45-60	17.9	9.4	8.5	19.3	45.7	17.1	0.62	7.5	7.0	6.6	93.9	0
C ₁	>60	19.3	11.4	7.9	16.2	51.4	13.1	0.46	7.6	7.3	5.8	96.5	traces

Profile No.: MP - 2

Location: *Hamuliakovo*
Soil unit - M.S.C.S.: *Fluvizem typická karbonátová* - FMmc
- F.A.O.: *Calcaric Fluvisol* - Jc
Parent material: *Calcareous alluvial sediments*
Physiography: *Slightly wavy alluvial plain of r. Danube*
Land use: *Arable land*
Altitude: *129 m*
Ground water table - former (Oct. 1992): *5 - 6 m*
- present: *2.5 - 3 m*

Soil description:

Aoncp - 2,5Y 4/3 moist matrix colour, medium textured, fine to medium crumb structure, very friable consistence, calcareous, many very fine to medium roots, clear smooth boundary to
(0-23 cm)
Aonc - 2,5Y 4/3 moist matrix colour, medium textured, fine medium crumb structure, very friable consistence, calcareous, many very fine to medium roots, gradual boundary to
(23-30 cm)
A/Cc - 2,5Y 4/4 moist matrix colour, medium textured, fine to medium textured, fine to medium crumb structure, very friable consistence, calcareous, common very fine to fine roots, gradual boundary to
(30-45 cm)
C(Go)c - 2,5Y 5,5/4 moist matrix colour, few fine faint Fe₃⁺ mottles, medium textured, structured, very friable consistence, calcareous, few very fine roots, clear wavy boundary to
(45-80 cm)
A'(Go)c - 2,5Y 4/2 moist matrix colour, few fine faint Fe₃⁺ mottles, medium textured, subangular to angular blocky structure, friable consistence, calcareous, none roots.
(>80 cm)

120 - 180 cm: fine sand

180 - 290 cm: sandy clay loam

290 - 340 cm: silt loam

340 - 400 cm: sandy gravel (sand - 25 %)

400 - 600 cm: sandy gravel (sand - 8-10 %)

Some analytical data of the profile No. MP - 2

1. Particle size distribution (mm) in %

Horizon	Depth	Sample	>0.25	0.25-0.05	0.05-0.01	0.01-0.001	<0.01	<0.001
	in cm	depth (cm)						
Aoncp	0- 23	10- 20	1.43	33.72	29.90	23.61	34.95	11.34
Aonc	23- 30	23- 30	0.79	36.37	29.17	20.98	33.67	12.69
A/Cc	30- 45	30- 40	0.43	24.43	34.60	28.24	40.54	12.30
C(Go)c	45- 80	55- 70	0.59	20.68	39.54	28.71	39.19	10.48
A' Go)c	80-120	85-100	0.68	33.86	27.95	27.12	37.51	10.39

2. Agrochemical properties

Horizon	pH	pH	CO ₃ ²⁻	P	K	Mg	N-NO ₃	N-total
	H ₂ O	KCl	%	mg.kg ⁻¹				
Aoncp	8.2	7.7	30	55	167	86	13	1 470
Aonc	8.5	7.9	10	55	29	130	7	1 219
A/Cc	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C(Go)c	8.5	7.9	30	18	26	246	4	1 182
A' (Go)c	8.3	8.0	33	22	22	522	4	1 000

3. Sorption properties

Horizon	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Sum of bases	CEC
	mval/100 g	mval/100 g	mval/100 g	mval/100 g	mval/100 g	mval/100 g
Aoncp	10.8	1.4	0.33	0.54	13.07	16.4
Aonc	12.0	2.0	0.29	0.10	14.99	16.7
A/Cc	-	-	-	-	-	-
C(Go)c	11.0	2.4	0.23	0.06	13.79	15.7
A' Go)c	9.0	4.9	0.47	0.06	14.43	15.7

Moisture regime of soil unit No. MP-2

Precipitation

Water content dynamics in layer 0-1m

Ground water table

4. Physical properties

Horizon	ϕ_s (g.cm ⁻³)	ϕ_d (g.cm ⁻³)	P (vol.%)	Pn (vol.%)	$\theta_{RK_{24}}$	θ_{MCC}	θ_W	θ_{DA}	K_s (m.d ⁻¹)	V_a (vol.%)
Aoncp	2.71	1.22	54.84	13.69	33.24	36.64	10.2	24.02	0.78	18.20
Aonc	2.70	1.33	50.68	8.08	37.18	39.62	11.8	27.03	0.42	11.06
A/Cc	2.70	1.34	50.44	9.49	35.18	37.48	10.5	25.31	1.20	12.96
C(Go)c	2.74	1.34	51.04	9.45	35.22	38.00	6.0	23.53	0.58	13.04
A' (Go)c	2.75	1.37	50.06	6.93	37.48	40.20	4.5	24.29	0.68	9.86

ϕ_s - particle density

ϕ_d - bulk density

P - total porosity

Pn - non-capillary porosity

$\theta_{RK_{24}}$ - retention water capacity

θ_{MCC} - maximal capillary capacity

θ_W - wilting point

θ_{DA} - point of decreased soil water availability

K_s - saturated hydraulic conductivity

V_a - minimal air capacity

5. Humus content and its quality

Horizon	C_{ox} %	Humus %	C_{HA} % to C_{ox}	C_{FA}	$C_{HA/FA}$	Q 4/6
Aoncp	1.10	1.90	20.3	15.4	1.37	4.28
Aonc	0.92	1.59	14.6	18.7	0.80	3.80
A/Cc	0.69	1.19	11.1	15.4	0.75	3.82
C(Go)c	0.48	0.82	-	-	-	-

Profile No.: MP - 9

Location: *Gabčíkovo*
Soil unit - M.S.C.S.: *Čiernica typická karbonátová - ČAm^c*
- F.A.O.: *Fluvi - calcareic Phaeozem - Hcf*
Parent material: *Calcareous alluvial sediments*
(medium textured on sandy)
Physiography: *Slightly wavy old alluvial plain of r. Danube*
Land use: *Arable land*
Altitude: *114 m*
Ground water table - former (Oct. 1992): *1.2 - 2 m*
- present: *1.2 - 2 m*

Soil description:

Amlcp - 10YR 2,5/2 moist matrix colour, few fine Fe₃⁺ mottles, medium textured, weakly developed subangular blocky structure, porous, very friable consistence, calcareous, fine to very fine common roots, clear boundary to
(0-30 cm)

Amlc - 10YR 2,5/2 moist matrix colour, few fine Fe₃⁺ mottles, medium textured, angular blocky structure, very firm consistence, calcareous, fine to very fine few roots, gradual boundary to
(30-40 cm)

A/CGroc - 2,5Y 4/2 moist matrix colour with many distinct Fe₃⁺ mottles, medium textured, prismatic structure, very firm consistence, calcareous with small nodules of CaCO₃, fine to very fine few roots, gradual boundary to
(40-55 cm)

C₁Groc - 2,5Y 5/2 + 6/6 moist matrix colour with many distinct Fe₃⁺ mottles, sandy loam texture, structured, friable consistence, calcareous with many small nodules of CaCO₃ (Ø 5 mm), none roots, clear boundary to
(55-80 m)

C₂Groc - 2,5Y 5/2 + 6/8 moist matrix colour with many distinct Fe₃⁺ mottles, loamy sand texture, structured, loose consistence, calcareous, without nodules of CaCO₃, none roots, gradual boundary to
(80-115 cm)

Gr - 2,5Y 5/2 + 6/8 (5/2 > 50 %) moist matrix colour, light (sandy) texture, structured, loose consistence, calcareous, none roots.
(>115cm)

115 - 240 cm: gray sand

240 - 300 cm: sandy gravel (sand - 35 %)

Water regime of soil unit No. MP-9

Some analytical data of the profile No. MP - 9

1. Particle size distribution (mm) in %

Horizon	Depth in cm	Sample depth (cm)	>0.25	0.25-0.05	0.05-0.01	0.01-0.001	<0.01	<0.001
Amlcp	0- 30	10- 20	0.54	18.78	26.60	33.68	54.08	20.40
Amlc	30- 40	35- 40	2.74	16.50	30.83	50.83	50.66	19.83
A/CGroc	40- 55	40- 50	1.30	19.82	32.74	25.45	46.14	20.69
C ₁ Groc	55- 80	65- 75	2.07	15.47	40.73	29.24	41.73	12.49
C ₂ Groc	80-115	90-100	1.26	55.24	30.04	9.33	13.46	4.13
Gr	>115	120-130	0.12	64.90	25.24	4.64	9.74	5.10

2. Agrochemical properties

Horizon	pH H ₂ O	pH KCl	CO ₃ ²⁻ %	P mg.kg ⁻¹	K mg.kg ⁻¹	Mg mg.kg ⁻¹	N-NO ₃ mg.kg ⁻¹	N-total mg.kg ⁻¹
Amlcp	8.2	7.6	25	60	90	637	92	2 660
Amlc	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A/CGroc	8.4	7.9	30	17	36	411	47	975
C ₁ Groc	8.6	8.1	40	12	14	401	16	1 252
C ₂ Groc	8.5	8.1	35	15	11	321	9	1 047
Gr	8.5	8.1	29	16	4	216	12	173

3. Sorption properties

Horizon	Ca ₂ ⁺ mval/100g	Mg ₂ ⁺ mval/100g	Na ⁺ mval/100g	K ⁺ mval/100g	Sum of bases mval/100g	CEC mval/100g
Amlcp	17.0	3.0	0.29	0.33	20.62	27.4
Amlc	-	-	-	-	-	-
A/CGroc	10.8	4.0	0.36	0.12	15.28	20.1
C ₁ Groc	6.0	4.0	0.42	0.00	10.42	14.8
C ₂ Groc	6.0	2.2	0.36	0.00	8.56	10.9
Gr	5.6	0.4	0.27	0.00	6.27	6.2

Moisture regime of soil unit No. MP-9

Water content dynamics in layer 0-1m

Ground water table

4. Physical properties

Horizon	φ_s (g.cm ⁻³)	φ_d (g.cm ⁻³)	P (vol.%)	P _n (vol.%)	$\theta_{RK_{24}}$	θ_{MCC}	θ_W	θ_{DA}	K _s (m.d ⁻¹)	V _a (vol.%)
Amlcp	2.67	1.31	50.86	12.99	34.20	37.20	17.2	27.40	1.10	13.66
Amlc	2.73	1.48	45.62	9.84	34.10	36.04	16.2	26.94	0.95	9.58
A/CGroc	2.74	1.56	42.86	8.37	32.66	34.42	13.7	25.08	0.14	8.44
C1Groc	2.75	1.56	43.38	8.20	33.20	34.64	8.8	23.44	0.14	8.74
C2Groc	2.77	1.51	45.38	6.35	37.96	39.06	6.7	25.46	0.17	6.32
Gr	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

- φ_s - particle density
 φ_d - bulk density
 P - total porosity
 P_n - non-capillary porosity
 $\theta_{RK_{24}}$ - retention water capacity
 θ_{MCC} - maximal capillary capacity
 θ_W - wilting point
 θ_{DA} - point of decreased soil water availability
 K_s - saturated hydraulic conductivity
 V_a - minimal air capacity

5. Humus content and its quality

Horizon	C _{ox} %	Humus %	C _{HA} % to C _{ox}	C _{FA} % to C _{ox}	C _{HA/FA}	Q 4/6
Amlcp	2.00	3.45	20.3	20.7	1.03	3.62
Amlc	0.77	1.33	11.4	9.8	1.18	4.03
A/CGroc	0.35	0.60	-	-	-	-
C1Groc	0.19	0.33	-	-	-	-
C2Groc	0.15	0.26	-	-	-	-
Gr	-	-	-	-	-	-

Name und Anschrift des Verfassers:

Bohumil ŠURINA
 Soil Fertility Research Institute
 Gagarinova 10
 827 13 Bratislava
 Slovak Republic